

Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

D. Banerjea

Former, Sir Rashbehary Ghose Professor of Chemistry, Calcutta University, Kolkata-700 009, India

E-mail : banerjeas2005@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 24 December 2015, accepted 14 January 2016

Abstract : An over-view of the major developments in inorganic chemistry since its modern origin in Europe in the late eighteenth century up to the present are broadly covered in this article, with mention of only notable contributions by chemists, omitting much of technical details for which the cited references be consulted. Emergence of the modern Indian school is briefly presented.

1. Introduction

Chemistry is of ancient origin in the arts and crafts of men in ancient civilizations of the World (including India, since *ca.* 2500 B.C.^{1,2}). But modern chemistry evolved in Europe in the 17th century, through a period of *alchemy* (13th-14th century) and *iatrochemistry* (15th-16th century), with the recognition by Robert Boyle the individual identity of various gases known at that time, and the distinction between elements, compounds and mixtures, apart from the gas laws he proposed that bear his name.

The work of the French chemist A. L. Lavoisier (during 1775-1776) which established the role of oxygen in combustion processes, that led to demolition of the *phlogiston theory* of Stahl (17th century), is generally considered the beginning of modern inorganic chemistry. Lavoisier also noticed that oxides of non-metals are acidic.

In his treatise "The Sceptical Chymist" (London, 1661) Robert Boyle discussed the criteria to decide if a substance is an *element* or not. The concept of elements which was more modern in a sense is seen in "Traite Elementaire de Chimie" (Paris, 1789) of A. L. Lavoisier, who of course mentioned heat and light also as elements. The concept of elements evolved further over the next few decades to reach the present state^{3(a),(b)}.

Robert Boyle also made hydrogen (in 1671) by dissolving metallic iron in dilute acids. He independently developed a process for making Phosphorus from urine and deposited his recipe with the Secretary of The Royal Society which was published (*Phil. Trans.*, 1692, 17,

583) after the death of Robert Boyle in 1691.

The element Phosphorus was first made by the German alchemist and physician H. Brand. J. D. Kraft who heard of it from Brand made a sample of the glowing substance that he showed to Robert Boyle who in his article "The Aerial Noctiluca" mentioned about its glowing property (in air) and that it is a constituent of living matter.

Developments during the late 1700s up to the early 1800s resulted in the discovery and characterization of a number of the elements, analysis and characterization of many minerals, syntheses of a variety of inorganic compounds and more rational approach to describe matter on an atomic basis^{3(c)}.

Credit for discovery of nitrogen (in 1772) goes to Daniel Rutherford.

Joseph Priestley prepared oxygen (in the year 1774). C. W. Scheele prepared it earlier but did not publish the result until 1777. Hydrofluoric acid was made by Scheele in the year 1771. During the 1770s Priestley made N₂O, NO and NO₂. During the period 1792 to 1808 all the *laws of chemical combination* were formulated based on fairly systematic studies. Significantly, two of these laws (*law of equivalent proportions*, Richter, 1792; *law of constant proportions*, Proust, 1799) were formulated before John Dalton proposed the *atomic theory* (in 1803). Indeed, this atomic theory was proposed to account for the *law of multiple proportions* (1803) in chemical reactions observed by him. Dalton published (1808) his views in a well developed form in his "A New System of Chemical

Philosophy". In order to account for the *law of gaseous volumes* of Gay-Lussac (1808), without violating the Daltonian view of indivisibility of atom (which is now known to be true only in all ordinary chemical reactions), Avogadro introduced the concept of molecules (*Avogadro's hypothesis*, 1811) .

In this connection it is worth noting that the Indian philosopher Kanada, propounder of the Vaiseshika system of Indian philosophy, proposed the atomic concept of matter in *ca.* 6th century B.C.; similar views were expressed by the Greek philosopher Democritus almost a century later (see Ref. 2, p. 17).

Originally, inorganic chemistry was primarily concerned with the chemistries of the individual elements, but since the 1950s has expanded into a multi-disciplinary science with considerable overlap not only with other branches of chemistry but also a variety of scientific disciplines extending from biological science to solid state physics. This is why inorganic chemistry is now often evasively defined as that branch of science which inorganic chemists pursue. However, there is a general agreement that an inorganic chemist is one who is broadly conversant with the chemistries of all the elements, besides the profound knowledge which he may have in his limited specialised domain of interest.

2. Discovery of elements

This is an useful parameter on the progress of inorganic chemistry (of chemistry in general) and the information is summarised in Table 1. Only 30 elements were discovered by 1800 A.D. and another 52 were discovered by 1900 A.D. But isolation/characterization of the rest including those (of atomic number up to 112) made artificially by nuclear reactions were achieved in the 20th century, and by 2010 the elements of atomic numbers 113-118 had been made by nuclear reactions (only a few

Table 1. Discovery of the Elements

Period/Age	Elements discovered
Prehistoric	Carbon, Sulfur, Gold
<i>ca.</i> 3000 B.C.	Silver, Copper, Lead, Tin, Mercury, Iron
<i>ca.</i> 500 B.C.	Zinc known as its alloy with copper (brass), but extraction of zinc from the mineral calamine was first achieved in India in the 9th century A.D., in China in the 16th century A.D., and in Europe in the 17th century A.D.
1600-1800 A.D.	Hydrogen, Nitrogen, Oxygen, Fluorine, Phos-

Table-1 (contd.)

	phorus, Arsenic, Tellurium, Antimony, Beryllium, Titanium, Chromium, Manganese, Cobalt, Nickel, Bismuth, Zirconium(ZrO ₂), Molybdenum, Tungsten, Platinum, Uranium
1801-1863 A.D.	Boron, Silicon, Chlorine, Bromine, Iodine, Selenium, Lithium, Sodium, Potassium, Rubidium, Caesium (Cesium), Magnesium, Calcium, Strontium, Barium, Cadmium, Aluminium (Aluminium), Indium, Thallium, Yttrium, Lanthanum, Cerium, Vanadium, Niobium, Tantalum, Thorium, Palladium, Ruthenium, Rhodium, Osmium, Iridium, Zirconium(metal), (Didymium) ^a , (Terbium) ^b
1868-1899 A.D.	Helium, Neon, Argon, Krypton, Xenon, Scandium, Gallium, Germanium, Praseodymium, Neodymium, Samarium, Gadolinium, Dysprosium, Holmium, Thulium, Polonium, Radium, Actinium, (Ytterbium) ^c
1903-1940 A.D.	[Technetium], [Promethium], Europium, Lutetium, Hafnium, Rhenium, [Astatine], [Francium], Protactinium, Radon, [Neptunium], [Plutonium], Heavy Hydrogen (Deuterium) having atomic mass double that of ordinary hydrogen (discovered by Urey and Murphy, in the year 1931); its natural abundance is 0.0156 per cent ^d
1944-1970 A.D.	[Americium], [Curium], [Berkelium], [Californium], [Einsteinium], [Fermium], [Mendelevium], [Nobelium], [Lawrencium], [Rutherfordium], [Dubnium]
By 1990 A.D.	[Seaborgium], [Bohrium], [Hassium], [Meitnerium]
By 1996 A.D.	[Darmstadtium], [Roentgenium], [Copernicium]
By 2010 A.D.	[E-113, Ununtrium], [Flerovium], [E-115, Ununpentium], [Livermorium], [E-117, Ununseptium], [E-118, Ununoctium]

^aDidymium was reported by Carl Mosander in the year 1843, but later shown to be a mixture of two elements Praseodymium and Neodymium. Their separation was effected by C. F. Auer von Welsbach in the year 1885.

^bTerbium was discovered by Carl Mosander in the year 1842 and from this another element Dysprosium was isolated by Lecoq de Boisbaudran (in the year 1886).

^cYtterbium was discovered by J. D. G. Marignac in the year 1878, and from its salts G. Urbain separated another element Lutetium by process of fractional crystallization of the salts repeated 15,000 times. Similarly, A. C. James made Thulium in a pure form by fractional crystallization of its salt repeated 15,000 times.

^dIn recognition of this H. C. Urey was awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1934. Incidentally, Tritium (hydrogen isotope of atomic mass number 3) was discovered by Rutherford and co-workers in the year 1934 as a product of a nuclear reaction. It is radioactive (half-life 12.3 years); its natural abundance is *ca.* 3×10^{-16} %. The most exotic and extremely transient ($t_{1/2} \sim 10^{-22}$ s, $\sim 10^{-23}$ s for ⁷H) isotopes of hydrogen of mass numbers 4, 5, 6 and 7 have been detected as products of nuclear reactions⁵.

atoms in some cases) and characterised so far. Available evidences show that there was considerable knowledge of metals in ancient India^{2,4}. A comprehensive account of the discovery of elements is available⁴⁽ⁱ⁾.

The class of elements from Lanthanum (atomic number 57) to Lutetium (atomic number 71), which have very closely related properties, are known (popularly) as members of the *rare earth* family. Their chemistry dates to the isolation of two supposedly pure “earths” (metal oxides), viz. Yttria by J. Gadolin in the year 1794 and Ceria by M. H. Klaproth, J. J. Berzelius and W. Hisinger in the year 1803. During the next about 100 years application of extremely tedious methods of fractionation, particularly fractional crystallization of the salts, led to resolution of Yttria into pure compounds of Yttrium, Gadolinium, Terbium, Dysprosium, Holmium, Erbium, Thulium and Lutetium, and of Ceria into compounds of Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium, Neodymium, Samarium, Europium and Gadolinium by the year 1907⁶. Since the 1950s far less tedious methods of separation by fractional elution by complex forming agents from ion-exchange columns were introduced for commercial production of these elements in pure form, while very pure samples are made on smaller scale by solvent extraction methods^{7,8}.

All the elements up to Uranium (atomic number 92), except Technetium (atomic number 43), Promethium (atomic number 61), Astatine (atomic number 85) and Francium (atomic number 87), occur in nature with natural abundance varying from very high (such as oxygen and silicon) to very low (mercury, 0.08 ppm; bismuth, 0.008 ppm).

Names of elements which do not occur in nature and made artificially by nuclear reactions⁹ are enclosed in square brackets [] in Table 1. This includes all the elements of atomic number higher than that of Uranium (atomic number 92). Most of these *trans-uranium elements* have been given proper names approved by the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC), except a few for which proper names have not been provided so far (the IUPAC approves a name only if proposed by the discoverer) and these are therefore referred to (as per IUPAC recommendation of 1979) by Latinised words expressing their atomic numbers (see Table 1).

The *trans-uranium elements* Neptunium (atomic number 93) and Plutonium (atomic number 94) were made in the year 1940 by McMillan and Abelson; a less stable isotope of Plutonium was reported by Seaborg *et al.*, in the year 1940. On consideration of electronic configurations Seaborg predicted (in 1944) the *Actinide Hypotheses*, viz. like the 14 elements after lanthanum forming the *lanthanides* (Ln), due to gradual filling of the 4f orbitals, there should be a similar series (*actinides*, An) due to filling of the 5f orbitals after actinium ending in the element of atomic number 103. During the period 1944-1958 Seaborg *et al.*, did succeed to make the remaining members of this series from Americium to Nobelium (of atomic numbers 95-102). The last member of this series (Lawrencium, atomic number 103) was made in the year 1961 by scientists of the Berkeley group (in USA). E. M. McMillan and G. T. Seaborg shared the Nobel Prize (1951) for their seminal contributions on *trans-uranium elements*.

While the E-118 was reported (only 3 atoms) in the year 2001 and its confirmation reported in the year 2006, the E-117 was first made in the year 2010¹⁰ and its confirmation reported in the year 2014¹¹; only a few atoms could be made.

These synthetic production of *super-actinide* elements have been reported by groups working at laboratories in Berkley (USA), GSI laboratory (in Germany) and Dubna (in Russia). A survey of heavy elements (*trans-actinides*), their synthesis and naming, appeared in the year 2009^{12(a)}. A review on the discovery of the elements E-113 to E-118 was published^{12(b)}. Review on the chemistry of elements E-104 onwards has been published^{12(c)} and there is a recent report on the synthesis of super-heavy elements at GSI, Darmstadt (Germany)^{12(d)}, and of evidence for discovery of E-113, E-115 and E-117^{12(e)}. Confirmation of E-113, E-115, E-117 and E-118 has now received IUPAC's approval [*Nature*, January 4, 2016]. This completes the 7th period of the Periodic Table. Prospective synthesis of elements beyond E-118 has been discussed^{12(f)}.

The interest in lanthanides (Ln) and actinides (An) is evident from the fairly large number of reviews on various aspects of lanthanide and actinide chemistry, including applications of their complexes and of their organometallic compounds published recently^{13,14}. Several others are on activation of small molecules by metal complexes¹⁵ (see also Sect. 4(J)), such as conversion of CO₂ to useful

products like oxalate^{15(g)}, organolanthanide^{16(a)} and organoactinide^{16(b)} chemistry, photochemistry of actinides and their complexes¹⁷, aqueous chemistry of trans-actinide elements¹⁸, production and properties of trans-uranium elements¹⁹, synthesis of super-heavy elements by “cold” fusion²⁰. Applications of lanthanides in magnets²¹ and as phosphors²², complexes of Terbium for MRI and fluorescence imaging²³ and as luminescent sensors²⁴, role of lanthanides in molecular magnetism²⁵ and in magnetic refrigeration²⁶ have been reported.

In India there is much ongoing research activity on lanthanide and actinide chemistry at the Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, at Mumbai (India) (private communication from Dr. V. K. Jain, Head of the Chemistry Division, BARC, Mumbai).

Uranium is of importance because it provides the “fuel” for nuclear reactors used for power generation. The abundance of uranium in the lithosphere is 2.3 ppm, and 0.71 per cent of the natural uranium is its isotope of mass number 235. This isotope undergoes fission on irradiation with neutrons of low energy (thermal neutrons) releasing an enormous amount of energy due to mass lost in the process, and following Einstein’s relation the amount of energy is given by $E = mc^2$ (c being the velocity of light, which is nearly 3×10^{10} cm per second). Natural uranium has another isotope of mass number 234 (0.006%) and the rest is the isotope of mass number 238. This U-

238 on irradiation with neutrons of appropriate energy (as in a breeder reactor) gets transformed into Pu-239 which is fissile and can serve as a fuel in a nuclear reactor. There is an enormous amount (*ca.* 4 billion metric tons) of uranium in sea water and research activity for economical recovery of uranium from sea water by ion-exchange²⁷ and complex-forming extraction²⁸ techniques are continuing. Extractants for partitioning of actinides have been reported²⁹.

Discovery of the element Promethium (atomic number 61) was the subject of much controversy for over two decades since 1926 (Ref. 9, p. 89) and its natural occurrence had been claimed and disputed. This element was subsequently identified³⁰ in the neutron irradiated fission products of U-235 (an isotope of uranium having a natural abundance of 0.71%). The elements Technetium (atomic number 43), Astatine (atomic number 85) and Francium (atomic number 87) were made/detected as products of nuclear reactions in the years 1937, 1940 and 1939 respectively.

3. Some other developments of significance during the 19th and first half of the 20th Century

Some of the most significant developments in inorganic chemistry and in other areas that had an impact on the progress in inorganic chemistry are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Some significant developments (see Text)

Year	Item	Year	Item
1807	Sodium and Potassium metals by electrolysis of fused MOH (Davy)	1808	Magnesium, Calcium, Strontium, Barium in metallic form (Davy)
1811	Nitrogen trichloride, NCl ₃ (Dulong)	1831	H ₂ SO ₄ , Contat Process ^(a)
1827-31	Platinum-olefin complexes including Zeise’s salt (Zeise)	1832-33	Laws of electrolysis (Faraday), magnitude of unit charge
1848	Law of effusion of gases (Graham)	1848	Zinc dimethyl (Frankland)
1852	Joule-Thomson effect, liquefaction of gases	1860-65	Determination of atomic weights (Stass)
1861	Na ₂ CO ₃ , Solvay process ^(b)	1865	NH ₂ OH.HCl (Lossen)
1867	Law of mass action (Guldberg and Waag)		
1868-69	Atomic volume curve (L. Mayer)	1869	Periodic law (Mendeleev)
1869-71	Periodic Table (Mendeleev)	1873	Molecular weight from vapour density (Victor Meyer)
1875	Gallium discovery (Boisbaudran)		
1886	Isolation of fluorine (Moissan)	1886	Germanium discovery (Winkler)
1886	Hall-Herault Process (aluminium from bauxite by electrolysis)	1887	Electrolytic dissociation theory (Arrhenius) (1)

(contd.)

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

Table-2 (contd.)

Year	Item	Year	Item
1888	Mond process (nickel extraction/ purification as Ni(CO) ₄)	1887	N ₂ H ₄ (Curtis)
1888	Ostwald's dilution law	1888	Le Chatlier's principle
1889	Activation energy of reaction (Arrhenius)		
1890	[Pt(NH ₃) ₄][PtCl ₃ (NH ₃) ₂]	1890	Molecular weight by limiting density (Bertholet)
1890	Hydrazoic acid, HN ₃ (Curtis)		
1891	NH ₂ OH (Bruyn)	1893	NaOH, Electrolytic Diaphragm process
1893	Coordination theory (Werner) (2)		
1894	Discovery of Helium in minerals (Ramsay)	1894	Separation of Neon, Argon, Krypton and Xenon from air (Rayleigh) (3)
1895	X-Rays (Roentgen) (4)	1896	Radioactivity (Becquerel) (5)
1897	NaOH, Castner-Kellner process ^(c)	1898	Radium and Polonium from pitchblende (P. and M. Curie) (5)
1897	e/m value of electron (Thomson) (6)	1899	Actinium (Debiegne)
1900	RMgX (Grignard) (7)		
1901	Oxidation of ammonia to NO (8) (Ostwald process for nitric acid)	1904	Accurate atomic weights (Richards) (9)
1906	N ₂ H ₄ preparation (Raschig)	1907	Hexol complex (Werner)
1907	{Pt(CH ₃) ₃ I} ₄ (Pope)	1909	Ammonia synthesis (Haber-Bosch) (10)
1910	Polynuclear complexes of Co and Cr		Haber-Bosch process (10)
1910-12	Isotopes (evidence, Thomson)	1912	Hexol complex (having no carbon) resolved (Werner)
1910	Isotopes in natural radioactive series (Soddy) (11)	1911-20	Isotopes of nine non-radioactive elements (Aston) (12)
1911	Electron charge value (Millikan) (13)	1911	Nuclear atom model (Rutherford)
1912	X-ray crystallography (Braggs) (14)	1912-36	Boranes (Stock)
1913	Atomic theory (Bohr)	1913-14	Atomic number of elements from X-ray spectra (Moseley)
1916	Electronic theories of valence (Kossel, Lewis, Langmuir)	1919	Transmutation of elements (Rutherford)
1920	Hydrogen bond (Latimer and Rodebusch)	1919-21	Coordinate bond (Lowry and others)
1923	EAN Rule (Sidgwick)	1923	Strong electrolytes (Debye and Huckel)
1926	Trans effect (Chernyaev)	1925	Rehnum discovery (Naddack and Tacke)
1931	H ₂ Fe(CO) ₄ , HCo(CO) ₄ (Hieber)	1926	Wave-mechanical atom (Schrodinger) (15)
1932	Discovery of neutron (Chadwick) (16)	1933	[Rh{SO ₂ (NH) ₂ } ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂], resolution of this having no carbon (Mann)
1934	Artificial radioactivity (Curie and Joliot) (17)		
1937	Technetium made (Perier and Segre)	1939	Fission of Uranium (Hahn, Meitner and Strassman) (18)
1939	Francium made (Perey)	1949	¹⁴ C Dating (Libby) (19)

^(a)Earliest preparation of H₂SO₄ was achieved in India by distillation of alum (*Rasarnava*, 12th cent. A.D., *Rasapradipasudhakaar*, 13th cent. A.D.) and later by distillation of green vitriol (*Rasaratnasamuchchaya*, 14th cent. A.D.), but in Europe in the 16th cent. A.D. by the same process. The Lead Chamber process for manufacture of H₂SO₄ was introduced in Europe in the year 1746; the Contact Process, using Platinum catalyst, was introduced in the year 1831, and almost a century later (mid 1920s) the presently used process with V₂O₅ as catalyst was introduced. H₂SO₄ is an important industrial chemical having various uses and the amount of H₂SO₄ manufactured in a country is
(contd.)

Footnote to Table-2 (contd.)

regarded as an index of its industrial progress.

^(b)The LeBlanc process for manufacture of Na_2CO_3 was introduced in Europe in the year 1773.

^(c)Earlier NaOH was made by the Lime-Soda Process (mentioned in the *Charaka Samhita* ca. 3rd cent. B.C., extant ca. 4th cent. A.D., and in the *Susruta Samhita* of an earlier period); the same process was used in Europe since 15th cent. A.D.

(1) For this S. Arrhenius was awarded Nobel Prize, 1903.

(2) In recognition of this Alfred Werner was awarded the Nobel Prize in 1913, being the first such ward for research contribution in Inorganic Chemistry.

(3) For this Lord Rayleigh was awarded Nobel Prize, 1904.

(4) For this W. C. Roentgen was awarded Nobel Prize, 1901.

(5) H. A. Becquerel was awarded Nobel Prize (1903) for discovery of the phenomenon of radioactivity in uranium salts. The scientist couple P. and M. Curies discovered (1898) two much more strongly radioactive elements Radium and Polonium in pitchblende (a uranium mineral) and for this they shared the Nobel Prize (1903) with Becquerel. Working with one ton of pitchblende the Curies succeeded in isolating pure Radium Bromide (a few mg only) and for this M. Curie received the Nobel Prize (second time) in the year 1911. E. Rutherford received the Nobel Prize (1908) for his investigations on radioactive disintegration of elements and chemistry of radioactive substances.

(6) For this J. J. Thomson was awarded Nobel Prize, 1906.

(7) For this V. Grignard was awarded Nobel Prize, 1912.

(8) For his contributions in catalysis, reaction rate and equilibrium W. Ostwald was awarded Nobel Prize, 1909.

(9) T. W. Richards was awarded the Nobel Prize (1914) for this contribution.

(10) F. Haber was awarded Nobel Prize (1912) for developing the catalytic process.

(11) F. Soddy was awarded Nobel Prize (1921) for this.

(12) F. W. Aston was awarded the Nobel Prize (1922) for discovery of isotopes of non-radioactive elements using an improved mass spectrograph devised by him.

(13) R. A. Millikan was awarded the Nobel Prize (1923) for experimental evaluation of the electronic charge (unit charge).

(14) W. H. Bragg and W. L. Bragg (father and son) were awarded (1915) the Nobel Prize for inventing and developing the X-ray crystallographic technique for determination of crystal structures.

(15) E. Schrodinger and P. A. M. Dirac shared the Nobel Prize (1933) for development of the wave-mechanical description of the atom.

(16) J. Chadwick was awarded (1935) the Nobel Prize for this discovery.

(17) In recognition of their seminal contribution in this field, the couple F. Joliot and Irene Joliot-Curie (daughter of P. and M. Curies) were awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1935.

(18) Otto Hahn was awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1944 for this discovery.

(19) For this W. F. Libby was awarded Nobel Prize in the year 1960.

4. Advances during the period since the 1930s (other than those already mentioned in Table 2)

(A) Modern views on chemical bonding :

During the period ca. 1930s-1950s significant advances were made to account for chemical bonding and interpreting the structures and properties of molecular species.

Development of the *atomic orbital (valence bond) theory*, originally proposed by Heitler and London³¹ and developed by Slater³² and more extensively by Pauling³³, is one such major development. Pauling also invoked the concepts of *resonance*, *hybridization* and *electronegativity* to account for stability and stereochemistry of covalent species and partial ionic character (polarity) of a

hetero-atomic covalent bond^{33(c)}. In recognition of his contributions Linus Pauling was awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1954.

The *electronegativity* concept first introduced by Pauling in the year 1932 has since then been defined in many ways and its precise interpretation has been debated³⁴. But despite this, Pauling's electronegativity values are still widely used to account for many observed facts of chemistry concerning stabilities and reactivities of compounds.

It is worth noting that in ca. 1st century A.D. the Jains in India expressed their views on chemical combination that bear formal resemblance to the *Dualistic Theory* of Berzelius (1812 A.D.). Their further view that ele-

ments of similar property combine when they differ significantly in the intensities of their properties shows its resemblance to the electronegativity concept of Pauling (see Ref. 2, p. 19). For the covalent halides of an element the bond energy increases with increase in electronegativity of the halogen in the sequence $I < Br < Cl < F$.

Parallel to the development of the atomic orbital theory, the *molecular orbital* (MO) concept of covalent bond formation was developed mainly by Hund³⁵, Mulliken³⁶ and Lennard-Jones³⁷. This latter viewpoint is indispensable for polyatomic molecules of much complexity such as clusters of high nuclearity. Even in cases of some simple molecules like O_2 , NO_2 , B_2H_6 , C_6H_6 , XeF_6 , SF_6 , etc., and in explaining the properties of coordination complexes, the molecular orbital view of bonding has certain decided advantages over the valence bond approach³⁸. But the valence bond approach is much easier to visualise and in this the classical view of a covalent bond as a force well directed in space and stereochemistry of molecular species are mostly retained.

The *valence shell electron pair repulsion theory* (VSEPR) that followed from the suggestions of Sidgwick and Powell³⁹ and extended and put into a more modern form by Gillespie and Nyholm⁴⁰ proved to be of much success in accounting for the shapes of covalent species (molecules and ions) in a simple manner.

A new point of view on *hypervalency* has been proposed⁴⁰⁽ⁱ⁾, and a refined value of $6.02214082 \times 10^{23}$ for the Avogadro's number has been reported⁴⁰⁽ⁱⁱ⁾.

The *ligand field theory*, which is a more sophisticated version of the electrostatic *crystal field theory*, developed in the 1930s^{41(a)-(d)}, has been used^{38(a),41(e),(f)} extensively since the late 1940s to account satisfactorily for the magnetic properties, stereochemistry, absorption spectral features, thermodynamic stabilities and kinetic labilities of coordination complexes.

Another development is the concept of *chemical hardness* of a species introduced by Pearson which has many useful applications; he also defined a *hardness parameter* in terms of ionization energy and electron affinity of the species and reported values for atoms, radicals, molecules and ions, and defined *softness* parameter as the reciprocal of the hardness parameter⁴². Yamada and Tanaka reported another softness parameter⁴³.

A parallel development is the *hard-soft acid base* (HSAB) principle for classification of Lewis acids and bases, which is of much use⁴⁴. This was a follow-up of an earlier classification of Lewis acids (metal ions) into *class a* and *class b*⁴⁵.

Various solvent parameter have been proposed to quantify the solvating and ionising power of a solvent⁴⁶, two of these being the solvent *donor number* (DN)⁴⁷ and solvent *acceptor number* (AN)⁴⁸. This concept of DN/AN was criticized by Drago^{49(a)} as according to him this presents only half of the information available from the *Drago-Wayland equation*^{49(b),(c)}. For reactions in different solvents (mixed solvents) the dependence of rate on the solvent parameters provides useful information on reaction mechanism⁵⁰.

Several *nucleophilicity* scales have been proposed⁵¹ for relative strengths of nucleophiles, which are of much use in nucleophilic displacement reactions.

In a solution of a strong acid (like HCl) even at a concentration above 0.1 M the concept of pH for expressing acidity (ability to protonate a base) loses its significance. For such systems the *Hammett acidity function*⁵² is of much utility and helps in elucidating the mechanism of an acid catalysed process (see Ref. 38(a), Chap. 8).

Another development worth mentioning is the application of *orbital symmetry rules*, originally developed for organic reactions⁵²⁽ⁱ⁾, to inorganic reactions including those of metal complexes⁵²⁽ⁱⁱ⁾.

(B) Advances in boron chemistry :

The chemistry of *boranes* (boron hydrides) began in the year 1912 with the pioneering investigations of these compounds by Stock that continued for the next almost 20 years⁵³. During the period since 1950 the chemistry of boranes and the structurally related *carboranes* has been one of the major areas of research activity in inorganic chemistry. Apart from their academic interest some such compounds are useful in many ways, such as high energy fuel, reagents of synthetic use and even of potential medical applications such as in *boron neutron capture therapy* (BNCT). Investigations of the molecular structures and interpretation of bonding in the boranes have been carried out by W. N. Lipscomb⁵⁴, in recognition of which he received the Nobel Prize in the year 1976.

Polymeric materials containing Lewis acid boron sites and their applications as luminescent and optical materials, and chemical and electrochemical sensors have been reported⁵⁵. Organoboron compounds have been reported to have optical, electronic and sensory applications⁵⁶. *Borols* are heterocycles having BC₄ ring; such species of higher stability have been reported that are useful as electron transporting and accepting materials in light emitting diodes and photovoltaics⁵⁶⁽ⁱ⁾.

The exotic salt K₅[B(SO₄)₄] having tetrahedral B(+3) has been structurally characterised⁵⁷ as also M₂[B(CN)₃] (M = Li, Na, K) having B(+1)⁵⁸.

(C) *Chemistry of noble gases* :

On theoretical considerations Pauling (1931) and Pimental (1951) had predicted likely formation of compounds by the members of the noble gas family (Group 18 of modern Periodic Table). But due to the then prevailing views on valency these suggestions did not receive much attention. An accidental observation (1960) by Bartlett and Lohman that O₂ reacts with red-brown vapour of PtF₆ forming the orange coloured [O₂]⁺ [PtF₆]⁻ led Bartlett to try out a similar reaction of Xe with PtF₆, since the ionization energy of Xe is very close to that of O₂, and he succeeded in making [XeF]⁺ [PtF₆]⁻ and [XeF]⁺ [Pt₂F₁₁]⁻⁵⁹; this was followed by the preparations of a number of other compounds of Xe, viz. fluorides, oxofluorides, fluoro complexes, oxides, oxoacids and their salts during the next few years⁶⁰, followed by many other much more novel types of compounds such as [M(XeF₂)₃][AsF₆]₂ (M = Pb, Sr), [Ln(XeF₂)₃][AsF₆]₃, [Mg(XeF₂)₄][AsF₆]₂, etc., having M-F-Xe-F bonding of each XeF₂, and others having even XeF₄, XeF₆ and KrF₂ and various M⁶¹, and also those in which Xe is bonded to a variety of other elements including metals^{62,63}, in some of which like [AuXe₄]²⁺ [Sb₂F₁₁]₂⁻ and analogous one having [HgXe]²⁺ the Xe acts as a typical ligand⁶⁴; this activity is continuing. Some compounds of Kr (krypton) have also been reported which are less stable than those of Xe⁶⁵.

There has been significant progress on ¹²⁹Xe NMR based biosensors for *in vivo* molecular imaging⁶⁶.

(D) *Advances in chemistry of silicon* :

Silicon has a rich variety of chemical and physical properties and is in fact one of the key elements in mod-

ern technology⁶⁷. Ultra-pure semiconductor grade silicon is used in solar cells for trapping of solar energy and its conversion to electricity. Most popular since the 1990s are the polycrystalline silicon solar cells.

Dark green crystals of an aromatic chair-shaped Si₆ ring compound^{68(a)}, a compound of Si(+1) with an Si-Si bond^{68(b)} and the polysilicide ion, Si₉⁶⁻, as a salt with a crown-ether complexed alkali metal cation^{68(c)} have been reported.

The organosilicon compounds have been another fertile field of research and well over 1,00,000 such compounds have been made. During the period since *ca.* 1960s polymeric materials belonging to the class of *siloxanes* (*silicones*), such as silicone oils, silicone greases, silicone elastomers and resins, have been made commercially, being some of the major industrial products that have many important uses⁶⁹.

(E) *Materials for new generation of solar cells* :

The next generation of solar cells are the *dye-sensitised solar cells* (DSSC) developed mostly through research contributions of Gratzel *et al.*⁷⁰⁻⁷⁷. The sensitizers (dyes) are complexes of ruthenium(II) with bipyridine derivatives as ligands. Their main advantage is that they are much cheaper, although have lower efficiency (up to 11% reported so far) and self-life. There is much ongoing research to improve both self-life and efficiency.

The latest generation of solar cells are the *bulk heterojunction* (BHJ) solar cells⁷⁸⁻⁸⁸ which are based on photo-sensitive semi-conducting polymers of low band gap and have decided advantages over the DSSC types and are also much less expensive than the silicon cells. Conversion efficiency of up to *ca.* 10 per cent has been reported to have been achieved with materials of low band gap that are efficient energy harvesters in the entire wavelength region of flux of solar radiation.

(F) *Polyphosphazenes* :

These are chain polymers having ...(-PR₂=N-)_n... skeleton. (PNCl₂)_n was the first such compound made in the 19th century (Liebig and Wohler, 1834). Several hundreds of such compounds have been made so far with a variety of physical properties (as fibres, foams, films, elastomers and rigid plastics). They have significant flame-retardant property⁸⁹ and have other potential ap-

plications due to anti-HIV activity of low toxicity⁹⁰, as stabilizer for vaccine⁹¹, other biomedical applications⁹², and also have optical, electronic and sensory applications⁹³.

(G) Novel organometallic compounds :

In this connection the *Dewar-Chat-Duncason* (DCD) model for metal-alkene bond is worth noting⁹⁴. In simple non-technical language this bond may be visualised as resulting from electron donation (sigma) to the metal from the double bond of the alkene (olefin) with some back-bonding (pi) from the metal to the olefin (interpreted on MO view), the extent of which depends on the nature of the metal (electronic configuration of the metal atom) and substituents in the alkene. The idea is extendable to the metal-alkyne (acetylene) bond as well. The bond has been named as μ -bond. A further development is the fully delocalised bond which is involved in metal-arene and other such unsaturated cyclic molecular species. This type of bonding is noticed in several thousand of such compounds known. The most important example is the orange coloured *ferrocene*, $\text{Fe}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, discovered accidentally by two independent groups⁹⁵. This melts at 173 °C and decomposes above 500°C, and illustrates exceptional stability of an organic species on being bonded to a metal. Its discovery provided impetus to many subsequent developments in organometallic chemistry⁹⁶.

Structure of ferrocene has been elucidated by X-ray crystallography⁹⁷ and nature of bonding has been proposed⁹⁸ based on the MO concept. The molecule of ferrocene has two parallel C_5H_5 rings with the Fe held centrally in between the two rings, with all the Fe-C bonds of the same length; the Fe (formally Fe^{2+}) thus appears “sandwiched” between the two rings (formally C_5H_5^-) with equal bonding interaction with all the C atoms of each of the rings (denoted by η^5) and hence the rings are bonded to the Fe as a whole, called *sandwich bonding* and the structure as *sandwich structure*. Similar sandwich compounds (*metallocenes*) are known with all the d-block and most of the f-block metals. Important properties of metallocenes have been reviewed⁹⁹.

Preparation of $\text{Zn}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2$ ¹⁰⁰ and of $[\text{M}(\text{cp})_2]^+[\text{Si}(\text{NMe}_2)_3]^-$ (M = Li, Na, K; cp = C_5H_5)¹⁰¹ are significant developments.

Also known are *bent sandwich* like $\text{M}(\text{cp})_2\text{X}$, $\text{M}(\text{cp})_2\text{X}_2$, $\text{M}(\text{cp})_2\text{X}_3$ (cp = C_5H_5) which have angular

(cp)-M-(cp); *half-sandwich* like $(\text{cp})\text{V}(\text{CO})_4$, $(\text{cp})\text{Mn}(\text{CO})_3$ (piano-stool structure), *mixed-sandwich* like $(\text{cp})\text{M}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)$ and *multi-decker sandwich*¹⁰², like $[(\text{cp})\text{Ni}(\text{cp})\text{Ni}(\text{cp})]^+$, $[(\text{cp})\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)\text{Co}(\text{cp})]$, $[(\text{cp})\text{Li}(\text{cp})\text{Li}(\text{cp})\text{Li}(\text{cp})]^-$ and even penta- and hexa-deckers¹⁰²⁽ⁱ⁾. Analogous to C_5H_5^- and C_5Me_5^- is $\text{B}_2\text{C}_3\text{R}_3^{3-}$ present in $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)\text{Co}(\text{B}_2\text{C}_3\text{R}_3)\text{Ni}(\text{B}_2\text{C}_3\text{R}_3)\text{Ni}(\text{B}_2\text{C}_3\text{R}_3)\text{Co}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)]^-$ ^{102(b)}. A non-carbon analogue of $\text{M}(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ is $\text{Ti}(\eta^5\text{-P}_5)_2$ ¹⁰²⁽ⁱⁱ⁾; other examples of $\eta^5\text{-P}_5$ are in $(\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Fe}(\eta^5\text{-P}_5)$ ¹⁰²⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾ and $(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Cr}(\text{P}_5)\text{Cr}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)$, in this the P_5 is bridging ($\mu\text{-}\eta^5$, $\eta^5\text{-P}_5$)^{102(iv)}.

The bonding in the “bent sandwich” has also been discussed¹⁰³.

In the year 1955, Fischer and Hafner reported¹⁰⁴ synthesis of *bisbenzenechromium*, $\text{Cr}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_6)_2$, which is iso-electronic with $\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$ mentioned above, and has a similar sandwich structure and similar bonding pattern. The polyphenyl compounds of chromium which F. Hein reported in the year 1919 are now known to be similar sandwich complexes of benzene, C_6H_6 , and diphenyl, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-C}_6\text{H}_5$ ¹⁰⁵. Many other metal-arene complexes have been made subsequently¹⁰⁶. In recognition of their significant and independent contributions on the chemistry of such sandwich compounds E. O. Fischer and G. Wilkinson were awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1973.

Similar sandwich, half-sandwich and mixed sandwich complexes are known to be formed by $\text{C}_7\text{H}_7^{3-}$ and $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8^{2-}$, as also by the *carbollide* ion, $(\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})^{2-}$, which can stabilise higher oxidation states of metals (like Cu^{III} , Ni^{III} and Ni^{IV}). An account of the present state of knowledge of these is available with pertinent literature references¹⁰². The compound $\text{U}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8)_2$ is known as *urnocene*. The bonding can be explained on MO view as for ferrocene¹⁰⁷.

Some uses of metallocenes have been reported, viz. ferrocene (0.05%) in fuel oils promotes smokeless combustion, ferrocene has anti-knock properties and even better is $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{C}_5\text{H}_4)(\text{CO})_3$; and many of the metallocenes are effective and superior catalysts^{108(a-c)} for polymerization of alkenes; they have several advantages over the traditional Ziegler-Natta catalyst^{108(d,e)} developed in the year 1955 by K. Zeigler and G. Natta independently, for which they were awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1963. A fullerene derivative for electrochemical sensing

of some cations and anions has been reported¹⁰⁹.

The reported synthesis of *hexaferrocenylbenzene*, $C_6(fc)_6$ ($fc = (C_5H_5)Fe(C_5H_4^-)$) is an important development in synthetic chemistry¹¹⁰.

The *carbene* and *carbyne* complexes of transition metals having M-C double and triple bond respectively have been reviewed¹¹¹.

(H) *Metal complexes for activation of dihydrogen, dioxygen and dinitrogen* :

Wilkinson prepared $RhCl(PPh_3)_3$ (*Wilkinson's catalyst*) which is a very effective and selective hydrogenation catalyst¹¹². Vaska¹¹³ reported $IrCl(CO)(PPh_3)_2$ (*Vaska's complex*) which is an effective O_2 activation catalyst for oxidation by O_2 . Complexes of chromium, cobalt and rhodium in low oxidation states¹¹⁴ also activate O_2 , as also a cobalt-porphyrin complex¹¹⁵ and some complexes of nickel¹¹⁶; some metalloenzyme model compounds¹¹⁷ are also effective.

It is worth noting in this connection that many metal complexes, particularly of cobalt(II), are capable of reversibly binding O_2 and there is profuse literature in this field¹¹⁸, and the first such report was made by Fremy in the year 1852.

Cobalt complexes (*salcomins*) of some Schiff base ligands were used during the World War II in portable oxygen generators (for isolation of O_2 from air) for use by the US Navy in welding and cutting operations^{118(c)}.

The first model of the dioxygen binding site of *hemoglobin* and *myoglobin* was a *picket-fence* porphyrin¹¹⁹. Several synthetic O_2 carriers have been made and there is a recent report on this¹²⁰.

Discovery (in 1965) of $[Rh(NH_3)_5(N_2)]^{2+}$ (the first complex of N_2 to be made, isolated as a salt) was a landmark event¹²¹. This was so much in conflict with the then prevailing views that the Editor of the *Journal of the American Chemical Society* rejected the report as unacceptable for publication, but fortunately that was accepted for publication in the *Chemical Communications* of the Chemical Society, London (now the Royal Society of Chemistry, UK). Dinitrogen complexes of most d-block and many of the f-block metals are now known; the N_2 in many of these can be reduced almost quantitatively or partly to ammonia, NH_3 , with or without some hydra-

zine, N_2H_4 , formation, by chemical reactions under easily attainable conditions, such as treatment with acid at ambient temperature as with complexes like $M(N_2)_2(PR_3)_4$ ($M = Mo, W$) reported by Chatt *et al.*¹²², or by reduction effected chemically¹²³ or electrochemically¹²⁴.

Activation of N_2 by metal complexes has been reviewed^{125,126}. Molybdenum complexes of PNP "pincer" ligands have been reported to catalyze the reduction of N_2 to NH_3 in presence of a proton source and an electron source¹²⁷. Highlights of recent developments in synthetic nitrogen fixation have been published¹²⁸.

There has been significant developments¹²⁹ in synthesis and characterization of nitrogen species higher than N_3 (known in hydrazoic acid and azides since long); some such species are N_4^{x-} ($x = 2, 4$, and also the novel N_2^{2-}), N_5^+ , the exotic salt like $(N_5)^+(N_5)^-$, and eighteen binary compounds of N and H (other than NH_3 and HN_3 , known since long).

(I) *Hydrogen the "green" fuel, its production and storage* :

With the fast depletion of sources of natural fuels (coal, natural gas, petroleum) there is a continuing search for alternative sources of energy. Moreover, burning of these carbon based natural fuels releases much carbon dioxide to the atmosphere which is a major factor for global warming due to the "greenhouse effect" of the carbon dioxide of which the concentration in the atmosphere has already reached an alarming level of *ca.* 400 ppm, and this is another reason for a search for a non-polluting fuel (green fuel). Nuclear energy is one option, but these are various problems associated with the production of nuclear energy, such as safe disposal of the highly radioactive spent "fuel" apart from radiation hazard in case of an accident in the nuclear power plant of which a few cases are well known, such as the one in the Chernobyl plant in the erstwhile Soviet Union in 1986 and The Three Mile Island Plant in the USA in 1979, and the latest one at Fukushima, in Japan, in early, 2011. However, till technological progress is made for commercially viable and cost-effective production of a non-polluting fuel nuclear power generation is unavoidable to meet the fast growing energy need in the world. In fact some countries are depending on nuclear power for meeting *ca.* 30–80 per cent of their energy needs, as against a meagre *ca.* 3 per cent

in India at present.

Hydrogen is the ideal non-polluting fuel; burning just 1g of hydrogen produces as much energy (heat) as is obtained by burning *ca.* 6g of coal. Burning of hydrogen produces non-polluting water and if appropriate technology can be developed to produce hydrogen from water on a large scale, without using fossil fuels as a source of energy, it becomes a renewable "green" energy. Hence, there is much ongoing research activity for generation of hydrogen from water using solar energy and also for proper storage of the hydrogen for its transportation. A breakthrough has been made in these areas which is briefly mentioned below.

Commercial production of hydrogen on a large scale as needed for production of ammonia by the Haber-Bosch process (catalysed reaction between nitrogen and hydrogen at high temperature and pressure) is by the *water-gas shift reaction*. Water-gas is mixture of CO and H₂ which is reacted with water when the CO reacting with H₂O forms CO₂ and H₂ from which CO₂ is removed by absorption in an amine. This water-gas shift reaction has long been carried out at high temperature in presence of a metal oxide catalyst¹³⁰. However, current interest is on homogeneous catalysts, some reported earlier, which work under far less drastic conditions (lower temperature and near ambient pressure). Several metal complexes have been reported to be suitable for the purpose¹³¹.

Much more recent interest is on photochemical generation of H₂ from water using sunlight in presence of a metal complex as the sensitizer¹³².

Photochemical generation of H₂ from water under sunlight using zinc-protoporphyrin-IX complex with recombinant human serum albumin has been reported¹³³. An efficient hydrogen producing system has been made by attaching a selenium-nickel-hydrogenase enzyme and a ruthenium dye sensitizer to TiO₂ particles which in contact with water releases H₂ on irradiation with sunlight¹³⁴.

Although gaseous or liquid hydrogen is currently an option for use as fuel in a prototype motor vehicle, solid state storage of hydrogen is superior both in terms of storage capacity and safety. Hence storage of large quantity of hydrogen in a compact solid medium from which the hydrogen can be released easily and conveniently as

and when needed is one of the challenges to be met for large scale use of hydrogen as a fuel¹³⁵ and there is considerable ongoing activity in this area, and major developments during the period up to 2008 have been reviewed¹³⁶. The storage can be broadly classified into chemical storage by a metal or metal alloys which form interstitial (non-stoichiometric) hydrides, or as stoichiometric metal hydrides or hydrido complexes, amidoborane derivatives, etc., or physical storage by substances having pores/cavities/channels in their structure that can adsorb and retain large quantities of hydrogen, such as *zeolites* and the more recently introduced (since 2003) *metal organic framework* (MOF) materials, as also the *covalent organic framework* (COF) materials¹³⁷.

(J) Zeolites, MOFs and COFs :

The *zeolites* are silicate minerals; some such synthetic materials have also been made and a total of *ca.* 200 such substances are now known. These have in their structures cavities in which charge-balancing cations are present which account for their ion-exchange properties. The *permutits* used in water "softening" belong to this class, but these have now (since 1960s) been mostly replaced by synthetic ion-exchange resins. The cavities (dia. 300–700 pm) permit their selective uptake of gases from gas mixtures, hence of use is separation of gases and as *molecular sieves*, as also their role as useful catalysts for specific reactions and also as catalyst support (particularly for metals of the platinum family)¹³⁸.

Recently it has been reported that certain zeolites do not act as simple molecular sieves, but rather separate molecules according to their ability to open "molecular trap-doors" within the zeolite structure. CO₂ molecules are particularly adept at sleeping through the trap-doors which is a promising discovery for industrial gas separation technologies such as "carbon capture". This discovery was made by Paul Webley at the University of Melbourne, Jefferson Liu of Monatsch University and their colleagues. They found that *chabazite* (a zeolite mineral) takes up CO₂ not only in preference to larger molecules (an expected behaviour of molecular sieve) but also in preference to smaller ones like CH₄. This is due to operation of the "trap-door mechanism" which depends on the charge-balancing cations that sit within the oxygen-rich nanopores of the negatively charged zeolite frame-

work and act as guards in the doorways through which the gas molecules can enter into the cavities in the zeolite structure. Only CO₂ (and not CH₄) can slip past the cation “guards” because of its electron-rich oxygen atoms. By interacting with the cation it makes the cation less tightly bound within the doorway so that the cation can move aside for the CO₂ molecule to slip through into the cavity of the zeolite structure. The cation then snaps back into place, preventing entry of other gases like CH₄¹³⁹.

The MOFs are coordination network having M^{m+} (or M_xⁿ⁺) bonded at donor sites of an organic polymer framework. These have pores/cavities within the structure which can be tuned to the desired size for a specific use and improving selectivity and hence these are more versatile than the zeolites. These are ideal for separation/purification of gases and storage of gases (like H₂, O₂, CO, CO₂, CH₄, etc.), use as catalysts for polymerization and photochemical reactions, and use of chiral MOF as catalyst for *asymmetric synthesis* of much use in the making of pharmaceuticals, fragrances, etc.^{140,141}. Nano-particles of ruthenium entrapped in MOF-5 has catalytic activity for a number of reactions^{140(b)}. Most promising use of MOFs is H₂ storage for fuel cells, storage of CH₄, sequestering CO₂, etc.^{141(a)}. A Mg-MOF selectively scavenges CO₂ from a 20% CO₂ + 80% CH₄ mixture trapping 89 g CO₂/kg of the MOF, and the trapped CO₂ can be completely released at 80°C^{141(e)}. Strategies to improve hydrogen storage capacity of MOFs have been reported¹⁴². MOFs with magnetic and ferroelectric properties have been reported¹⁴³. Electrically conducting thin films of MOFs have been made which are of potential application in photovoltaics, as sensors and making electronic materials for industry^{144(a)}. The MOFs are also of use in drug delivery and have other medical applications^{144(b)-(e)}. A mixed-valent manganese cluster complex having [Mn₄^{II}Mn₂^{III}(μ₄-O)₂]¹⁰⁺ structural units having MOF-like structure has been shown to have selective affinity to absorb CO₂ and not N₂ from gas mixtures. This also has catecholase-like catalytic activity¹⁴⁵. Incidentally, some complexes of Fe(II) have recently been reported as functional models of catecholase¹⁴⁶. Luminescent multifunctional lanthanide based MOFs have been reported¹⁴⁷.

The COFs are rather similar to MOFs but without the metals and are excellent hydrogen storage materials¹⁴⁸.

Incidentally some recent advances on *fixation of CO₂ forming useful chemicals* such as formate, oxalate, etc., are worth noting^{15,149,150}. A Ru catalyst that can efficiently convert atmospheric CO₂ to methanol by reacting with H₂ at 50 bar and 155°C, i.e. under much more milder conditions than in the earlier known methods, has been reported¹⁵⁰⁽ⁱ⁾. A complex of uranium(IV)¹⁵¹ reacts with CO binding and transforming 4CO into a squarate ion, C₄O₄²⁻. Similarly a dinuclear hydrido complex of tantalum reductively couples 6CO forming the non-cyclic C₆O₆²⁻ anionic species¹⁵². Photochemical reduction of CO₂ to CO in sunlight using zinc-porphyrin as photosensitizer and a complex of ruthenium as catalyst¹⁵³ is another important recent development; the CO can be converted to fuel using known technology and has other synthetic use.

(K) *New allotropes of carbon : fullerenes, carbon nanotubes, graphene :*

The *Fullerenes*¹⁵⁴ are a family of polyhedral carbon allotropes having an even number of carbon atoms, C_{2n}; there is at present mass-spectroscopic evidence for many of these species with *n* up to 300.

In the year 1985 a group led by H. W. Kroto (UK) and R. E. Smalley (USA) laser-blasted graphite (a common allotrope of carbon known since early periods) at a temperature of >10,000°C and mass-spectroscopically detected that the product contained a series of species C₄₄ to C₉₀, with C₆₀ followed by C₇₀ as major products, all having only even number of carbon atoms^{154(a)}. From an extract of the product in benzene, in which C₆₀ (dark reddish-brown solid, magenta colour in solution) and C₇₀ (black solid, port-wine red colour in solution) are soluble; the C₆₀ and C₇₀ were obtained in a pure form (in 1990) by chromatographic separation on a column of alumina^{155(a)}. Convenient preparation of bulk quantities of C₆₀ and C₇₀ have been reported^{155(b)}.

C₆₀ and C₇₀ have been detected in some natural minerals^{155(c)-(f)}.

The C₆₀ fullerene (*bucky-ball*) has a football-like spherical structure made up of 20 hexagonal C₆ and 12 pentagonal C₅ rings fused in a regular manner (as for the seams of a football).

In recognition of this discovery H. Kroto, R. E. Smalley and B. Curl were awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1996.

The fullerenes have very interesting chemistry^{156(a)} and their important properties have been reviewed^{156(b)}; many metal-encapsulated fullerenes are also well-known, e.g. $[M@C_{84}]$ ¹⁵⁷. There are medical and other technical applications of fullerene derivatives¹⁵⁸. The cytotoxic (anti-tumour) activity of C_{60} derivatives has been reported¹⁵⁹ and other medical applications¹⁶⁰. $C_{60}(OH)_8$ is useful in cancer drug delivery^{161(a)} and $C_{60}(OH)_{20}$ nanoparticles have antitumour activity^{161(b)}. Gadolinium fullerenes are of use in diagnostic MRI¹⁶². $[Gd@C_{82}(OH)_{20}]$ nanoparticles inhibit tumour growth and is useful in cancer therapy¹⁶³. C_{60} -containing nanostructured polymeric materials are of much promise for cancer therapy and treatment of multidrug resistant pathogens¹⁶⁴. A porphyrin- C_{60} is of use in photodynamic therapy¹⁶⁵ and C_{60} -based photosensitizer for photodynamic inactivation of pathogens in biological liquids has been reported¹⁶⁶. Fullerene-isoniazide conjugate has been reported which has excellent antimicrobial activity (but low toxicity) against *M. tuberculosis* and *M. avium*¹⁶⁷. Salts of some water-soluble polycarboxylic acid derivatives of C_{60} have been reported to have pronounced anti-HIV activity of low toxicity¹⁶⁸. Fullerene derivatives having *in vivo* low toxicity in combination with pronounced antiviral activity against HIV and influenza virus have been reported¹⁶⁹. A fullerene-acrylamide copolymer is water soluble and has antitumour activity against bone tumour cells¹⁷⁰. A carboxylic acid derivative of C_{60} is the preferred electron acceptor for BHJ solar cells mentioned in Sect. 4(E). Fullerene derivatives have important electronic and optical properties that make these useful in photo-electronics and sensory applications¹⁷¹. Thin films of co-deposited Ti- C_{60} have potential application as electrochemical materials¹⁷².

The effects of carbon nanoparticles on biological environment and the importance of these effects on human and animal health have been discussed¹⁷³. An interesting group of materials are the *carbon nanotubes* (CNT) prepared by evaporation of graphite. They are needle-like cylindrical tubes of graphitic carbon capped by fullerene-like hemispheres (see Ref. 9, p. 335). If the caps are removed and the tube is cut lengthwise and spread out a graphene (see below) sheet results. Fibres made of carbon nanotubes are very strong, and can be used to make bullet-proof fabric and armour of military use, making

high-strength ropes and electric cables (because of its high electrical conductivity¹⁷⁴). Emerging applications of carbon nanotubes have been reviewed¹⁷⁵; these are of considerable use in controlled drug delivery¹⁷⁶. Toxicity effects of CNTs have been reviewed¹⁷⁷. MWCNTs are useful MRI contrast agents¹⁷⁸, and SWCNTs are of use in medical imaging¹⁷⁹. Very recently B. Cola and coworkers (USA) have for the first time made a solar energy collector using carbon nanotubes that can directly convert light into electricity¹⁸⁰.

Graphene was discovered¹⁸¹ in the year 2004 by K. S. Nvoelov and A. K. Geim for which they were awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 2010. This is a planar sheet of fused C_6 rings and is in fact a single layer of the graphite structure (this results from stacking of such sheets which are held together by comparatively weaker attractive forces, see Ref. 9, p. 316). In its electrical conductivity graphene is superior to silver metal (which has the highest electrical conductivity of any material) and has the highest thermal conductivity of any material known so far. Its synthesis and applications are well documented in literature¹⁸². Many newer applications of graphene have been reported¹⁸³. It has been demonstrated most recently that materials composed of a single layer of atoms, such as graphene and that of the isoelectronic $(BN)_x$ (boron nitride) can function as a "sieve" to separate hydrogen and deuterium more effectively than almost any other process known so far¹⁸³⁽ⁱ⁾. This is of much promise in nuclear technology, such as making heavy water from ordinary water for use in nuclear reactors and preparing deuterium from ordinary hydrogen for use in fusion process in much cheaper way than at present.

A solution of CO_2 in water which was believed to contain carbonic acid, $OC(OH)_2$, contains only the hydrate, $CO_2.H_2O$ and no $OC(OH)_2$. But this elusive carbonic acid has been generated by Laser irradiation of bicarbonate and a proton acid and detected by femtosecond IR spectroscopy¹⁸⁴.

Researchers in the USA and China (PRC) have recently produced the new boron allotrope B_{40} which, unlike the fullerenes, have a box-like structure¹⁸⁵ having hexagonal and heptagonal holes and named it *borospherene*. A C_{60} -like B_{60} cannot be stable due to electron deficiency.

But this can be overcome by introducing a B atom into the centre of each B₆ hexagon in its structure forming B₈₆¹⁸⁶. Recently Chinese scientists (Y. Ma *et al.* of Jilin University, in the PRC) have carried out systematic structure-searching calculations and from the results predicted a stable fullerene-like B₃₈¹⁸⁷. Its isolation is awaited.

Phosphorene, the phosphorus analogue, and *silicene*, the silicon analogue of graphene have been reported¹⁸⁸.

(L) *Metal cluster compounds* :

These are the largest group of polynuclear compounds having two or several metal atoms in which there are metal-metal bonds¹⁸⁹. Advent of X-ray crystallography and other modern techniques of structure elucidation have led to the characterization of many such species, mostly since the 1960s.

The earliest known examples are the compounds of mercury(I) having [Hg-Hg]²⁺ units. Later species having [Hg-Hg-Hg]²⁺ and [Hg-Hg-Hg-Hg]²⁺ were characterised and many more having Hg-Hg and Hg-metal (other than Hg) bonds¹⁹⁰.

Several compounds of zinc and of magnesium in their +1 oxidation state (first such examples) having M-M bond (M = Zn, Mg) have been reported fairly recently (Zn¹⁹¹, Mg¹⁹²). Another interesting example is a compound having two Ba-Ga bonds¹⁹³; and more exotic compound having Ca-Fe bond¹⁹⁴.

Also to note here is that (as in the Hg(I) compounds) these M-M bonds are “unsupported” (without any bridging ligand between the metal atoms), unlike in many of the known clusters, such as most of the metal carbonyl and metal carbonylate clusters, which constitute a large class of metal cluster compounds. As an example, nickel is known to form many carbonylate clusters (lowest is [Ni₅(CO)₁₂]²⁻, highest known so far is [Ni₄₄(CO)₄₈]ⁿ⁻)¹⁹⁵.

Cluster formation is predominant for the d-block metals. But large cluster formation even by many main group (p-block) elements have been reported more recently, viz. having Al₇₇ in [Al₇₇{N(SiMe₃)₂}₂₀]²⁻¹⁹⁶ and Ga₈₄ in [Ga₈₄{N(SiMe₃)₂}₂₀]ⁿ⁻ (n = 3, 4)¹⁹⁷. Structures of these Al and Ga clusters have been reported and both are multi-endohedral species¹⁹⁷, i.e. M_x encapsulated in M_y polyhedron and this entire unit encapsulated in M_z polyhedron, viz. [Al@Al₁₂@Al₄₄@{Al(N(SiMe₃)₂)₂₀}]²⁻, and

[Ga₂@Ga₂₀@Ga₄₀@{Ga(N(SiMe₃)₂)₂₀}]ⁿ⁻ also having two terminally bonded (*exo*) Ga.

In cluster formation by the f-block metal uranium, several species of nuclearity 20, 68, 120 UO₂ units, have been reported¹⁹⁸. Cages of UO₂ peroxide can trap cations and anions¹⁹⁹.

Structure of the ternary cluster [Zn@Zn₅Pb₃Bi₃@Bi₅]⁴⁻ has been reported recently²⁰⁰; in the same article several other ternary clusters such as [Zn₆Sn₃Bi₈]⁴⁻, [Ni₂Sn₇Bi₅]³⁻, [Ni₂Pb₇Bi₅]³⁻, [Pd₃Sn₈Bi₅]⁴⁻, [CeSn₄Bi₉]⁴⁻, [EuSn₆Bi₈]⁴⁻ are also mentioned.

Several super-large clusters of very high nuclearity and their structures have also been reported, viz. Pt₃₀₉²⁰¹ and Pd₅₆₁^{202,203}.

Many clusters with interstitially held atom/atoms of an element E (B, C, Si, N, P, As, Be, Al, Ge, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni) are known²⁰⁴. The interstitial atom stabilizes the cluster as is the case with Ti₆CCl₁₄ which has Ti₆C cluster unit, but no simple Ti_x cluster without the interstitial atom is known²⁰⁵. There are other examples of such cluster stabilization by interstitial atom²⁰⁶. The hydrido-carbonylate [Co₆H(CO)₁₅]⁻ has H held interstitially within the Co₆ cluster^{207(a)}. But in the case of [H₂Rh₁₃(CO)₂₄]³⁻ the two H are not held interstitially but occupy the centres of two opposite square-faces of the Rh₁₂ cluster having an interstitial (endohedral) Rh^{207(b)}. Many heterometallic clusters are also well known, such as the Ag₁₂Au₁₃ in [Ag₁₂Au₁₃Br₈(PPh₃)₁₀]⁺^{208(a)} and a more recently reported Cu₁₇Mn₂₈ (having Cu(I), Cu(II), Mn(II), Mn(III) and Mn(IV))^{208(b)}.

The *metallocarbohedrenes* (*Met-cars*) also belong to the cluster class. These are a novel group of robust clusters of binary and ternary metal carbides having fullerine-type closed structures. A representative class being M₈C₁₂ (M = Ti, Zr, Hf, V, Fe, Cr, Mo, etc.) as also the heterometallic M_{8-x}Ti_xC₁₂²⁰⁹.

Metal clusters have useful applications, viz. (a) as catalysts²¹⁰, in nanoscience and nanotechnology²¹¹ and in microelectronics²¹².

The *Zintl* anions²¹³ and similar cations are called “naked clusters” as these polyatomic species (M_xⁿ⁻, M_xⁿ⁺) have only M-M bonds and no bridging or terminally bonded groups (ligands) bonded to the metal atoms. During 1920s-

1930s the German chemist Eduard Zintl carried out pioneering studies on the highly coloured species that were known to be formed on dissolving some metals in liquid ammonia solutions of alkali metals and identified several such anionic $[M_x]^{n-}$. But their characterization was possible much later by isolation of many of these as salts with large counter-cations like $[Na(crypt)]^+$ (crypt = a cryptand ligand (see Sect. 4(O))²¹⁴. Several homoatomic and heteroatomic species have been characterised, mostly obtained as salts of alkali and alkaline earth metals by thermal reactions between the metals in solid state at high temperature²¹⁵, as also quite a few endohedral ones like $[Ni@Pb_{10}]^{2-}$, $[Sn@Cu_{12}@Sn_{20}]^{12-}$, etc.²¹⁶. Several cationic $[M_x]^{n+}$ have also been reported²¹⁷.

The bonding in metal clusters, as for the boron clusters in the boranes, can be best described using the delocalised MO concepts of bonding (Sect. 4(A)). The type of polyhedron that represents the structure of a cluster can be predicted, almost without any exception, using the *skeletal electron counting rule* (*Polyhedral skeletal electron pair theory*, PSEPT), commonly referred to as *Wade's rules*²¹⁸, which have been elaborated further by others²¹⁹.

Much information is documented in literature on the bond order for the metal-metal bond in dinuclear clusters; numerical values from 1–4 are well known²²⁰. But more recently species having multiple bond of bond order 5 and 6 have been reported²²¹.

Compounds having Ln-M and An-M bonds have been reported recently²²².

(M) *Supramolecular inorganic and coordination chemistry* :

The superlarge clusters mentioned in the previous section belong to this class. There has been a surge of interest in many other types of supramolecular species including metal complexes since the 1990s and there has been exponential growth in research activity in this field in recent years which are well documented in literature^{222(i),222(ii)}.

(N) *New types of superconducting materials*^{223,224} :

Several superconducting alloys of niobium having T_C around 20 K were known until 1986, e.g. Nb_3Ge with T_C ca. 23 K; these are used to make wires for the windings of extremely powerful electromagnets which have many

uses, such as in NMR equipment used in the laboratories for structural investigations, studying rates of fast exchange reactions, etc., and in equipment for MRI (a medical diagnostic tool).

The first high temperature *non-metallic superconductor* (a mixed oxide of La-Ba-Cu) made in the year 1986 by Bednorz and Muller^{225(a)} had a T_C of 35 K. They were awarded the Nobel Prize for this work in the year 1987. This work was followed by the discovery by Wu, Chu and others of a mixed oxide of Y-Ba-Cu of T_C 95 K^{225(b)} and subsequently a few others (Tl-Ba-Ca-Cu mixed oxides) of T_C ca. 120 K were reported, and claim made for a superconducting mixed oxide (of Bi-Pb-Sb-Sr-Ca-Cu) having T_C value of 164 K (see Ref. 9, Chap. 24, Sect. 24.8.5).

(O) *Ligands and complexes* :

Nitrosyl and *carbonyl* complexes of metals having CO and NO as ligands respectively are well known, a few such compounds being known since the 19th century. But stable complexes of *thionitrosyl*, NS (no free NS has been isolated so far), and *thiocarbonyl*, CS (very unstable in free state), are more recent developments (NS²²⁶; CS²²⁷).

Hydride is a versatile ligand; many complexes of s, p and d block metals having hydride ligand are well known. But most remarkable is $Pt(H)(Cl)(PEt_3)_2$, a white solid distillable at 130°C *in vacuo* (pressure 0.01 mm Hg), stable to air, water and even dilute HCl solution²²⁸. Complexes of d block metals with H_2 as ligand are now well known; the first such compound made was $W(CO)_2(H_2)(PPr^i_3)_2$ ²²⁹.

All the commonly known bidentate ligands bind to two adjacent (cis) positions in a coordination complex. However, by suitable tailoring of the structure *trans spanning* bidentate ligands have been made that bind to two diagonally opposite (trans) positions in a metal complex²³⁰.

Some bidentate ligands (i.e. those which satisfy two coordination positions) may be mentioned because of certain interesting features. One of this is *rubeanate* (deprotonated rubeanic acid, dithioxamide) $[(S(NH)C-C(NH)S)]^{2-}$ which forms coloured very insoluble polymeric complexes with ions of Co(II) (brown), Ni(II) (blue) and Cu(II) (dark green)^{231(a)}. Ray used this as a microchemical reagent for the detection of these metal ions (even in mixtures, using paper chromatographic spot test

technique); in fact this is the most sensitive test for Cu^{2+} ion known so far (a detection limit of 3 ppb)^{231(b)}. He later used this and its derivatives for spectrophotometric determination of several metals²³².

During the period 1937 to 1958 P. Ray and his group carried out extensive studies on complexes of *biguanide*, $\text{H}_2\text{N}(\text{HN})\text{C}(\text{NH})\text{C}(\text{NH})\text{NH}_2$ (bigH) and several N(of NH_2)-substituted biguanides (all bidentate (N,N donor) ligands) and also a few dibiguanides (all 4N donors), particularly *ethylenedibiguanide*, which are well documented in a review published by Ray²³³ that has been referred to by the distinguished inorganic chemist M. T. Beck (Debrecen University, Hungary) as a "gold mine in the chemistry of complex compounds." This forms very stable coloured complexes with many of the d-block metals (in +2, +3, even +4 state as for Mn). Stabilities (thermodynamic) of the $[\text{M}(\text{bigH})_3]^{3+}$ were also reported by Ray and co-workers ($\text{M} = \text{Co}^{234(a)}$; $\text{M} = \text{Cr}^{234(b)}$). Structures of metal biguanide complexes have subsequently been established by UV spectroscopy^{235(a)} and X-ray crystallography^{235(b)}.

Subsequently, some former associates of P. Ray reported a few other metal biguanide complexes²³⁶, including mixed ligand complexes of Cr(III)^{236(d)} and of Ni(IV)^{236(e)}. The Mn(IV) complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{big})_3]^+$ has also been reported²³⁷. Earlier reported was $[\text{Mn}(\text{bigH})_2(\text{OH})_2]^{2+}$ ²³⁸.

Using ethylenedibiguanide as ligand (a quadridentate ligand, 4N donors) Ray and Chakravarty²³⁹ prepared a complex of silver(III) which is the most stable complex of Ag(III) known so far. Its thermodynamic stability has been reported^{240(a)} as also its inertness (kinetic stability)^{240(b)}. Its structure elucidated by X-ray crystallography has been reported²⁴¹.

Use of ligands having P and As as donors have been an area of much activity of J. Chatt and co-workers²⁴². The chelating *diars* ($o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{AsMe}_2)_2$) made by Chatt has also been much used as ligand by R. S. Nyholm and co-workers. They discovered a remarkable reaction of diars with CCl_4 forming the ionic $[\text{C}(\text{diars})_2]^{4+}$ isolated as salts²⁴³, and this is the first and so far the only known example of a ligand stabilised C^{4+} . Nyholm and co-workers (H. L. Nigam, D. V. Ramana Rao) also used *diars* to make heteroleptic carbonyls of several d-block metals (Fe,

Mn, Cr, Mo and W)²⁴³⁽ⁱ⁾.

Coordination chemistry of SbR_3 ligands has been reviewed²⁴⁴.

In connection with studies on the racemization of $[\text{Co}(\text{bigH})_3]^{3+}$ Ray and Dutt²⁴⁵ proposed intuitively the *rhombic twist mechanism* of racemization of tris-chelate complexes, being the first such mechanism to be proposed. Later Bailar proposed the *trigonal twist mechanism*²⁴⁶ for such process. A somewhat different twist mechanism was proposed by Springer and Sievers²⁴⁷. Experimental evidence has been furnished in favour of the Ray-Dutt twist²⁴⁸, also for Bailar twist²⁴⁹, and in some systems the results are consistent with racemization occurring concurrently by both the Ray-Dutt twist and the Bailar twist (*ca.* 80% and *ca.* 20% respectively in the system investigated²⁵⁰). On the basis of theoretical calculations it has been proposed²⁵¹ that Bailar twist should be favoured for complexes with chelating ligands having small 'bite' distance.

The *beta-diketonate* ligands (*dike*) have a rich coordination chemistry²⁵². They form very stable chelate complexes with most metal ions; the commonest of this class is acetylacetonato(1-) (*acac*). Species like $\text{M}(\text{dike})_3$ formed by M(III) are stable non-electrolyte *inner complexes* which can be vaporised at moderate temperature affording a method for separation/purification of metals. They decompose at higher temperature allowing their use in *metal organic chemical vapour decomposition* (MOCVD) technique for depositing thin films of pure metal oxides on a suitable surface²⁵³. Such complexes of chiral dike have applications as catalysts for chiral syntheses; they are of use for gas-chromatographic separation of isomers and optical enantiomers²⁵⁴.

The *triketonates* and *polyketonates* are versatile ligands (*compartmental ligands*) which can link two or more metal centres serving as bridges between them²⁵⁵.

The *alkoxides* and *aryl oxides* form species like $\text{M}(\text{OR})_n$ with M in oxidation state +n having quite rich chemistry²⁵⁶. Significant amount of research work on these have been done, notably by D. C. Bradley (UK) and R. C. Mehrotra (India)²⁵⁷. The *calyx[n]arenes* are an interesting class of macrocyclic aryl oxides having *n* phenolic OH as the metal binding sites²⁵⁸. These are molecules having a torus shape with potential to mimic some iron

bound enzymes²⁵⁹.

The *calyx[6]pyrrole* complexes halide ions²⁶⁰; complexation of anions is now a growing field²⁶¹; and anion complexing agents include *katapinates*²⁶², *anion cryptates*²⁶³ and *complexones for anions*²⁶⁴. P. A. Tasker described a novel system which on binding a metal ion templates to a form capable of anion complexation²⁶⁵. An interesting tellurium boryl Lewis acid for binding fluoride ion has been reported²⁶⁶.

For complexes of coordination number (C.N.) 6 octahedral structure was established by Werner on the basis of chemical evidences that was later proved by X-ray crystallographic structure determination in many cases. But trigonal prismatic structure is also now known for C.N. 6 in many cases²⁶⁷. The first example to be reported was the complex $[\text{Re}(\text{S}_2\text{C}_2\text{Ph}_2)_3]$ ²⁶⁸; similar complexes of several other metals with ligands of this class, $(\text{R}_2\text{C}_2\text{S}_2)^{2-}$, were reported subsequently²⁶⁹.

Syntheses and studies on complexing abilities of several macrocyclic (such as *crown ethers*)²⁷⁰, macropolycyclic (such as *cryptands*)²⁷¹, encapsulating ligands like *sepulchrates* and such other ligands of this class (*sarcophagines*)²⁷² are some developments worth noting. Using cryptand complexes of alkali metal cations it has been possible to isolate several exotic species as salts, viz. *alkalides* (having alkali metal as anion) like $[\text{Na}(\text{crypt-222})]^+\text{Na}^-$ ²⁷³, *electrides* (having the bare electron as the anion) such as $[\text{Cs}(18\text{-crown-6})]^+\text{e}^-$ ²⁷⁴, and the Zintl ions mentioned earlier (Sect. 4(L)).

Macrocyclic ligands which are useful as MRI/optical imaging agents responsive to zinc²⁷⁵ and copper²⁷⁶, which are useful for their detection, have been reported. An N_4 -cyclam ligand has been reported to be useful for the detection and discrimination of Pb(II) and Hg(II)²⁷⁷.

In this connection it is worth noting that the deep blue coloured solutions formed on dissolving alkali metals in liquid ammonia are known since early days (Weyl, 1864) and presence of solvated electron in these solutions was postulated by Kraus²⁷⁸ from observations on the electrical conductance of such solutions. But identification of *solvated electron* in aqueous solution was made by Hurt and Boag²⁷⁹. This was followed by significant research activity on the generation of solvated electron and studies of its properties including rates of reductions of aquametal

ions and metal complexes²⁸⁰⁻²⁸⁷.

Octopus ligands have been reported which complex the alkali metal cations more firmly than the *crown ethers* and almost as firmly as the *cryptands*²⁸⁸. A hexa-phenolic compound having a bowl-shaped cavity, forms a dimer in which the two units are held face-to-face by hydrogen bonding interactions enclosing within the cavity large cations like Rb^+ or Cs^+ forming a complex having a *clam-like* structure²⁸⁹.

Chelating ligands having bidentate function (denticity 2) are well known since Werner's time; but ligands of higher denticity viz. 3-6 were all reported in the 20th century, and evidence for octadentate function of a ligand was furnished by A. E. Martell in 1958-1960²⁹⁰. But a more definitive evidence for an octadentate ligand was presented later²⁹¹.

The first hexadentate ligand as its complex of Co(III) was reported by Dwyer and Lions²⁹². A common and well known hexadentate ligand is EDTA which forms exceptionally stable complexes with many metals. Initial studies of this and several other similar aminopolycarboxylates were reported by G. Schwarzenbach and co-workers²⁹³. EDTA is used routinely in titrimetric determination of some metals and is particularly useful for estimation of "hardness" of water (estimation of Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in the water sample).

Rebeck (Jr.) and co-workers²⁹⁴ reported a *syn-tetracarboxylate* ligand that has exceptional affinity for Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} ions; a 0.1% solution of this ligand in chloroform extracts over 99% Ca^{2+} and ca. 73% Mg^{2+} from an aqueous solution having 59 ppm Ca^{2+} and 24 ppm Mg^{2+} respectively.

(P) *Absolute configurations of chiral metal complexes :*

Development of spectroscopic methods (CD and ORD) for determination of absolute configurations of chiral complexes of metals is another major development of the 20th century²⁹⁵.

Asymmetric synthesis has been mentioned in connection with one of the uses of MOFs (Sect. 4(J)). Metal complexes of chiral ligands are of much use in such synthesis²⁹⁶.

(Q) *Stabilities of metal complexes :*

Considerable amount of work has been carried out,

particularly after J. Bjerrum's seminal work²⁹⁷ on the thermodynamic stabilities of metal complexes expressed by their formation constant values that can be evaluated by several methods, and the vast amount of accumulated literature data are well documented^{298,299}.

Based on such values several empirical correlations of stabilities of metal complexes with electronic properties of metal ions have emerged³⁰⁰, one of these is the *Irving-Williams natural stability order for metal complexes*³⁰¹.

Another conclusion that followed was that chelating ligands form more stable complexes, the stability increases with increase in the number of chelate rings; Schwarzenbach named this *chelate effect*³⁰². Macrocyclic ligands form even more stable complexes and Margerum referred to this as *macrocyclic effect*³⁰³. Both chelate effect and macrocyclic effect are also seen in the rates of formation and dissociation of metal complexes of such ligands³⁰⁴.

5. Bioinorganic chemistry

During the period since the 1950s very significant advances have taken place in the field of inorganic chemistry of relevance to biological chemistry, particularly on the role of metal ions and metal complexes in biological systems. This is evident from the publication of a multi-volume treatise³⁰⁵. An overview of the major developments are to be seen in a recent publication³⁰⁶; only a few significant rather recent developments will however be mentioned in this article.

Of all the elements that are to be found as constituents of a human body, 11 are essential metals the total amount of which is only *ca.* 4 kg for a healthy man (body weight *ca.* 70 kg), and of these a few are only in trace concentration and yet are vital; their deficiency causes disease condition but excess beyond a threshold level (that varies from metal to metal) is harmful and hence their concentration in a human body needs to be precisely regulated³⁰⁷. Most of these metals carry out their biological function as constituents of metallo-enzymes, which are the catalysts for such reactions. The enzyme devoid of the metal (the *apoenzyme*, a protein) completely loses its activity, but the apoenzyme has an important indirect role as this significantly modulates the behaviour of the bound metal ion for the desired selective function. Bioinformatics sur-

vey of 1371 different enzymes, for which three-dimensional structures are known, estimated that 47% of them require metals, with 40% of them containing metals at their catalytic active sites³⁰⁸. Much effort is being directed in making appropriate models that mimic the structures and functions of the active sites (metal bound sites) of the metalloenzymes³⁰⁶.

A significant development was the isolation and characterization by X-ray crystallography of the Mo-Fe-cofactor of a natural *nitrogenase* enzyme (involved in conversion of N₂ to NH₃) that shows that contrary to earlier belief the N₂ binding site in the enzyme for its reduction to NH₃ is Fe and cannot be Mo³⁰⁹.

Another development that needs mention is the role of NO which, despite being an atmospheric pollutant, is an important cellular signalling molecule in mammals including humans and is involved in many physiological and pathological processes³¹⁰. It is produced in the brain as a messenger molecule. Low levels of NO production is important in protecting organs, such as a liver, from ischemic damage. It is also a powerful vasodilator and helps to increase blood flow countering *atherosclerosis*; and this also helps in penile erection to counter impotency. All pain relieving drugs administered to patients suffering from *angina pectoris* act through release of NO; the same is true for anti-impotency drug *Viagra*. The hypotensive effects of hydroxamic acids may be due to their ability to rele NO, while many of their ubiquitous role in biology and medicine is surely due to their ability for chelating metal ions³¹¹. In recognition of its important biological role the journal *SCIENCE* of 1992 was dedicated to NO which was named the "Molecule of the year"; three US scientists received the Nobel Prize in the year 1998 for their contributions in elucidating the biological role of NO.

The biological function of NO involves its binding to metal (Fe, Cu) centre of metalloenzymes. Nitrosyl complexes of iron are known since long, such as sodium nitroprusside, Na₂[Fe(CN)₅NO]. But two nitrosyl complexes of copper have been reported recently³¹².

Rosenberg's discovery of antitumour activity of *cis*-PtCl₂(NH₃)₂ (*cisplatin*) was a landmark development³¹³ which prompted intense activity in searching for such others of comparable or higher potency and lower toxicity.

Cisplatin has been in use for treatment of various malignancies, especially testicular and ovarian cancer³¹⁴.

Drug targeting technologies to reduce the side-effects in using cisplatin have been reviewed³¹⁵. Platinum compounds of improved cytotoxicity against leukaemia and breast cancer have been reported³¹⁶. An entire issue of *Dalton Transaction* (published by the RSC, UK) of 2009 was devoted to metal anticancer compounds including those of platinum, one of silver and another of gold. Reviews of biochemical³¹⁷ and medicinal³¹⁸ applications of gold compounds have been published. Recent developments in ruthenium compounds as anticancer drugs have been reviewed³¹⁹. Some complexes of gold have applications in photodynamic therapy³²⁰.

Some silver complexes having antibiotic activity³²¹ and some gold complexes having antimicrobial activity³²² have been reported. A review on antimicrobial and anti-cancer properties of silver and gold compounds has been published³²³, and there is increasing application of nanoparticles of gold in cancer diagnosis and therapy³²⁴ and compounds of silver and gold as potential anti-tumour drugs (*loc. cit.*).

There are reports on antimicrobial, antibacterial and antifungal properties of silver complexes³²⁵. There are several recent reports on silver and gold compounds as potential antitumour drugs³²⁶⁻³³⁰. Copper chelation in cancer therapy has also been reported³³¹ and anti-HIV activity of a complex of copper³³².

A special issue of the *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry* of 2009 (Vol. 103) had several articles on biological role of vanadium, vanadium complexes as models of vanadium-enzymes, anti-diabetic compounds of vanadium and vanadium compounds of other medicinal use (many such uses are known). Vanadium complexes have been probed for their insulin-enhancing ability³³³. Spermicidal and cytotoxic property of vanadium compounds were investigated with promising results; their complexes having thiohydrazone ligands are significantly more effective than the commonly used metronidazole against amoebiosis³³⁴. Two complexes of tungsten have been reported that have insulin-mimic effect³³⁵.

A dinuclear Pt(II)-Ru(II) complex inhibits A β 42 aggre-

gation that occurs at an early stage of *Alzheimer's disease*³³⁶. Some important recent reports are the following : (a) compounds of gold as therapeutic agents³³⁷; (b) silver complex of high cytostatic activity on ovarian cancer³³⁸; (c) ligand coordination in enhancing antitumour and anti-malarial activity of a gold-phosphene complex³³⁹; (d) complexes of Au(III) of improved cytotoxicity³⁴⁰; (e) Au(III) complex having cytotoxicity against cisplatin-resistant cancer cells³⁴¹; (f) therapeutic potential of complexes of silver and gold³⁴²; (g) silver complexes for antimicrobial and anticancer applications³⁴³; (h) cytotoxic behaviour of complexes of silver and gold^{344,345} and of vanadium³⁴⁶; (i) role of metal ions (including Cu(II)) in neurodegenerative diseases³⁴⁷; (j) metal ions in the causation and treatment of *Wilson's disease* and *Alzheimer's disease*³⁴⁸; (k) application of inorganic chemistry for non-cancer therapeutics³⁴⁹. Chromium(III) complexes of some amino acids play a protective role in cerebral antioxidant defence system in diabetic patients³⁵⁰.

Of all the metals that are now known to have biological function, tungsten was the last one to receive recognition. A review of its biological role has been published³⁵¹.

Arsenic contamination of ground water has become a problem in many regions. Hence removal of arsenic from water by convenient and economically viable method is a challenging problem. A recent report that laboratory made hydrated ferric oxide, similar to the natural mineral *ferrihydrite*, selectively removes arsenic(III) from water is interesting. Efficiency of the material is improved by increasing the surface area. The absorbed As(III) can be removed by eluting with alkali solution and the material can be reused after a heat treatment, at least for ten cycles³⁵².

In recent years very sensitive and selective colorimetric probes for detection, and even estimation, of pollutants have been reported; some typical examples of which are for CO (in air)³⁵³, mercury (as Hg(II))³⁵⁴ and silver (as Ag⁺)³⁵⁵ in solutions.

A ferrocene derivative, in which each C₅ ring has a -NHCONHCH₂-(18-crown-6) substituent, has potential cation and anion binding sites and is a useful electrochemical probe for K⁺, F⁻ and H₂PO₄⁻ ions in solution³⁵⁶.

6. Dynamics of reactions and reaction mechanisms

Major work has been on metal complexes; many systems which do not involve conventional coordination complexes also come under this category in a broad sense, such as reduction of Cr(VI) in acid medium involving CrO_4^{2-} which may be viewed as Cr^{6+} coordinated by 4O^{2-} ligands.

Mechanisms of reactions of metal complexes received the attention of Alfred Werner who, based entirely on qualitative investigations, proposed the possibility of racemization of octahedral complexes $\text{M}(\text{A-A})_3$ by an intramolecular mechanism involving a chelate ring opening without dissociation of the A-A from the metal³⁵⁷. Evidence in support came later when Long reported³⁵⁸ that the bound oxalate in $[\text{M}(\text{ox})_3]^{3-}$ exchanges with free oxalate ion in solution exceedingly slowly compared to the rate of racemization. Another mechanism of racemization was proposed by Charonnat³⁵⁹ which assumed formation of an intermediate of C.N. 8. Evidence in support came from the observation³⁶⁰ that anhydrous $\text{K}_3[\text{Cr}(\text{ox})_3]$ racemizes extremely slowly on heating to 120°C compared to the hydrated salt. The twist mechanisms proposed later have been mentioned in Sect. 4(O).

In the early 20th century there was some sporadic research activity on rates of aquation of acido-ammine complexes of a few metals³⁶¹.

Since the late 1940s there has been profuse activity in this field initiated by F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson in the USA and M. L. Tobe (belonging to the school of C. K. Ingold, a Nobel Laureate, and R. S. Nyholm) in UK. Much of these initial developments are well documented³⁶² and had been the subject of a few published review articles^{363,364}, in one of which^{364(b)} the salient contributions in this field by chemists of India and of other countries in Asia were only highlighted (as per request of the publisher). Three more reviews were on substitution and redox processes in transition metal complexes^{365(a)}, a general one on inorganic mechanistic chemistry^{365(b)} and a short review on reactions of complexes of Pt(II) and Pd(II) containing nitrogen donor ligands^{365(c)}.

All the developments in this field are systematically presented and discussed in a recent publication (see Ref. 38(a), Chap. 8). Systemic research in this field was initiated in India by D. Banerjea with studies on ligand re-

placements reactions of Pd(II) complexes³⁶⁶; studies on many other systems followed^{363(d),(e),364(a)-(c)}.

The first systematic studies on ligand replacement (substitution) reactions of complexes of Pt(II) were reported by Banerjea, Basolo and Pearson³⁶⁷ which established the kinetic nature of the *trans effect* phenomenon, and which also paved the establishment of the general mechanism of ligand replacement reactions of complexes of Pt(II) and in general of square-planar complexes. To account for the observed facts they postulated that the square-planar complexes of Pt(II) exist in solution with two other ligands (solvent molecules) weakly attached axially. Authentic evidence for this has been furnished more recently³⁶⁸. The ligand replacement reactions of square-planar complexes of Pt(II) are best represented as an interchange (*I*) process in which bond formation by the entering nucleophile and dissociation of the departing ligand are synchronous, which accounts for the insensitivity of rates of such reactions to the overall charge on such complexes and also the magnitudes of the ΔV^\ddagger values for these reactions; but in contrast the analogous reactions of Au(III) complexes are associative (*A*) in nature³⁶⁹. Results of studies on square-planar complexes of Pd(II) are best regarded as interchange (*I*) process with significant bond dissociation of the departing ligand³⁷⁰.

All earlier studies were on systems where the rates were slow enough to be followed by conventional methods like conductometry, potentiometry and particularly spectrophotometry (for coloured complexes). With the advent of new techniques like flow methods (constant-flow and stopped-flow), T-jump and P-jump, NMR and EPR, since about 1960s, it has been possible to study many fast and ultra-fast reactions. M. Eigen and co-workers made pioneering studies on complex formation by labile metal ions (which react almost instantaneously) and developed the general mechanism for such processes (*Eigen-Tamm-Wilkins mechanism*³⁷¹) and in recognition of his contributions M. Eigen was awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1967, which he shared with R. G. W. Norrish and G. Porter who also made notable contributions in studies on extremely fast reactions. H. Taube was awarded the Nobel Prize in the year 1983 in recognition of his salient contributions on mechanisms of electron transfer reactions³⁷². R. A. Marcus was awarded the

Nobel Prize in the year 1992 for his contribution on theory of electron transfer reactions; he developed the *Marcus cross-relation* for estimating theoretically the rate constant of an outer-sphere electron transfer reaction³⁷³.

Photochemical reactions of metal complexes have been studied quite extensively³⁷⁴.

While research activities in various areas of the field are continuing, since ca. 2000 the emphasis is more on reactions of di- and polynuclear complexes and clusters, systems of relevance in biology, reactions of organometallic compounds etc. Two studies on MoFe₃^{375(a)} and Rh₄^{375(b)} cluster formation reactions were reported recently. Mechanism of DNA cleavage by dinuclear zinc complexes has been reported recently³⁷⁶.

R. Banerjee and co-workers reported their studies on the reduction of a well known dinuclear complex of Co(III) having a superoxo bridge ($\mu\text{-O}_2^-$) to the corresponding peroxo-bridged ($\mu\text{-O}_2^{2-}$) dinuclear complex³⁷⁷. Kinetic studies on oxidation of ON(SO₃)₂²⁻ by the superoxo-bridged dinuclear Co(III) complex has also been reported³⁷⁸. The Ru(III) complex [Ru(edta)(H₂O)]⁻ mimics *peroxidase* like activity; kinetics of its catalytic role in the oxidation of hydroxyurea has been reported³⁷⁹. Both outer-sphere (OS) and inner-sphere (IS) mechanisms operate in the oxidation of [Co(edta)]²⁻ by [IrCl₆]²⁻; contribution of the OS path is enhanced in presence of added [Co(en)₃]³⁺³⁸⁰. Activation of C-H bond by metal oxo complexes has been reviewed³⁸¹. Reactions of CO₂ with [W(OH)(S₂C₂Ph₂)₂]⁻ (a complex of W(IV) that functions as a *formate dehydrogenase* model) has been reported³⁸². Oxidation of ascorbic acid/ascorbate by a tetranuclear complex of Mn(IV) has been reported³⁸³. Results on catalytic role of a mixed-valent (Fe(III), Fe(II)) complex, a *phosphatase* model^{384(a)}, and of a Mn(III) porphyrin complex, a *superoxide dismutase* model^{384(b)}, have been published.

Possible pathways for base hydrolysis of [Co(NH₃)₅Cl]²⁺ have been investigated by DFT and molecular orbital methods³⁸⁵. Infrared photodissociation spectroscopy and photodissociation kinetic studies have been performed on [M(H₂O)_n]²⁺ (M = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Ca) providing insight into the shell structures and average C.N. (n) values of these aquametal ions³⁸⁶.

From the highlights of developments in inorganic chemistry published annually by the Royal Society of Chemistry, RSC (UK), viz. *Annual Reports on the Progress of Chemistry* (ARPC), Sect. A, during recent years since 2000, the following seem to be the major areas of current research activities, in addition to the chemistries of elements of different groups of the Periodic Table, including the Actinides and the Lanthanides : (a) Computational modelling of inorganic solids, (b) Macrocyclic coordination chemistry, (c) Supramolecular inorganic and coordination chemistry, (d) New compounds and structures in the solid state, (e) Nanoparticles and Nanotubes, (f) Fullerenes, (g) Mechanisms of reactions in solution, (h) Metal complexes-nucleic acid interactions, (i) Metal complexes as inorganic pharmaceuticals, (j) Photochemistry and photophysical properties of metal complexes, (k) Inorganic and organometallic polymers, (l) Radiochemistry, (m) Activation of molecules by coordination, (n) Hydrogen generation, (o) Nitrogen fixation.

It is indeed a matter of regret that the RSC has discontinued publishing the ARPC (Sects. A, B and C) from 2014.

7. Emergence of the modern Indian school

A fairly elaborate account of this is available in an earlier publication of the present author³⁸⁷ and hence only a brief survey will be presented here. Developments up to the early 1970s are well documented in "Progress of Chemistry in India", Part I, covering 50 years up to 1962 (Ed. P. Ray) and Part II, covering the period 1963-1972 (Eds. R. D. Tewari and A. K. Dey), published by the Indian Science Congress Association, Kolkata, in the years 1964 and 1974 respectively; a somewhat brief account of major developments is in a publication on Chemistry in Indian Universities (Ed. R. C. Mehrotra), published (1979 ?) by the University Grants Commission, New Delhi.

It is significant to note that during the period of 100 years from 1784-1883 there was tardy progress with only 24 papers in chemistry published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*; teaching of chemistry started at Medical College, Calcutta (now Kolkata), which was founded in the year 1835. During the period since the 1840s some chemistry related research work was carried

out in a few centres in India, which were mostly not in the domain of inorganic chemistry. It was Alexander Pedler who initiated teaching and some research work (in inorganic chemistry related areas) at Presidency College, Calcutta, in the year 1873, and also introduced holding of practical examinations for evaluation of knowledge and performance of students of the BA and MA courses in chemistry. In the year 1890 he published three papers in the *Journal of the Chemical Society (London)* on the action of sunlight on some chemical reactions and on the photoluminescence of phosphorus.

More systematic research was initiated by P. C. Ray after he joined the Presidency College, Calcutta, in the year 1889 after returning to India in 1888 with a D.Sc. degree of Edinburgh University, in Scotland, UK. Incidentally, the first Indian to acquire the said degree from the same university was Aghore Nath Chattopadhyay, father of one of India's revered leaders of the independence movement Smt. Sarogini Naidu (nee, Chattopadhyay) and of Harindranath Chattopadhyay, and an uncle of the present author's maternal grandfather. Although some towering personalities in science like J. Van't Hoff expressed highly of Aghore Nath's knowledge and intellect, it is indeed a misfortune for his countrymen that although he joined the Education Service in the then princely state of Hyderabad he never directed his efforts in the pursuit and advancement of chemistry by any research activity in India. This task was amply fulfilled by Prafulla Chandra Ray (P. C. Ray).

He not only initiated teaching of modern chemistry but made a much more significant contribution in establishing and nurturing the modern Indian School of Chemistry. In this connection the following extracts of authoritative opinion would be worth noting :

"Outweighing his achievements as a scientific worker, the creation and fostering of an Indian School of Chemistry will ever remain his conspicuous contribution towards national progress of Indians." – J. N. Mukherjee (a student of P. C. Ray).

"If a census were to be taken of all the Indian Chemists who have published any original work and if they were asked to indicate the source of their inspiration, I believe the majority would ascribe the credit to Sir P. C. Ray.....To the mind of an Indian, Bengal still

represents the intellectual province of India and Calcutta the metropolis.....Calcutta is the undisputed birthplace of modern chemical research in this country." – S. S. Bhatnagar (from his Presidential address delivered in the Chemistry Section of The Indian Science Congress, 1928).

It would be unfair to judge P. C. Ray, of multi-faceted personality, only on the basis of the merit of his research contributions, many of which are controversial and some of his suggestions regarding the constitutions of several of his compounds, valences of the metals etc., were indeed most astoundingly absurd, even judging on the basis of the level of knowledge and developments of his time, which have been elaborated earlier^{388,389}. But it is useful to illustrate this with an example. In the year 1924 he published a paper³⁹⁰ in which he reported a compound which, based on analytical data, was formulated (empirical composition) as $3(C_2H_4S).2(AuCl_3)$, and assigned to it a constitution that corresponds to $C_6H_6S_3.2AuCl_3$, i.e. short of six H compared to the empirical composition (difference not discernible from analytical data on Au, S and Cl only). The organic moiety $C_6H_6S_3$ was formulated as a cyclic tri-thioetone and the bonding of each one of the two $AuCl_3$ was proposed (very astonishingly) as $CS=AuCl_3$ thereby justifying his assumption that each Au is pentavalent. It is clear that even if such a compound was formed, the bonding of S to Au was by a coordinate bond with Au in the trivalent state as in the $AuCl_3$. The concepts of the electronic theories of valence, of the coordinate bond and Alfred Werner's coordination theory were already in a fairly developed state when P. C. Ray published this work, but obviously he was still obsessed with the classical concepts of valency. The above compound of P. C. Ray is most likely to be a dinuclear complex of Au(III), presumably $(R_2S)Cl_3Au(\mu-R_2S)AuCl_3(R_2S)$, where R_2S is $(C_2H_4)S$ ³⁸⁹. Similarly, for the species $2Et_2S.PtCl_3$ he proposed the astounding constitution $Et_2ClS-Pt^{III}Cl-SClEt_2$ with trivalent platinum and quadrivalent sulfur^{391(a)}. In a publication in the following year^{391(b)} he proposed the same compound to be a molecular compound of Pt(II) and Pt(IV) of composition $PtCl_2.2Et_2S + PtCl_4.4Et_2S$, but for the Pt to Et_2S bonding he astoundingly suggested $Pt---Et_2S$; in a subsequent publication^{391(c)} he correctly rep-

resented the bonding of an R_2S to Pt through S. In another publication^{391(d)} he more reasonably proposed that $PtCl_3 \cdot 2Et_2S$ is a mixed-valent complex of Pt(II) and Pt(IV), $[Pt(Et_2S)_4][PtCl_6]$. In his later publications on compounds of iridium^{391(e)} we notice his much more reasonable and systematic approach in proposing plausible constitutions.

When in 1896 P. C. Ray first announced³⁹² the discovery of mercurous nitrite there appeared a very appreciative comment in the journal *Nature*. But strangely, in practically none of the advanced level treatises on inorganic chemistry that were published during P. C. Ray's life time or thereafter there is any mention of this. On the contrary in "*Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry*", (Eds.) J. C. Bailar (Jr.) *et al.*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1973/1975, Vol. 3, p. 293, it is stated citing the investigations of Potts and Allred³⁹³ that mercurous nitrite is "too unstable to isolate" and that the hyponitrites of mercury, also reported by P. C. Ray, are "even more unlikely". An estimate of the enthalpy of formation of authentic mercurous nitrite showed this to be highly endothermic³⁹⁴, which accounts for its instability. Attempts to stabilise mercurous nitrite by complexing the Hg_2^{2+} by a crown-ether (as achieved in the case of mercurous perchlorate) ended in failure³⁹⁵. Three groups³⁹⁶ reported X-ray crystallographic studies on the supposedly mercurous nitrite without any chemical characterisation of their samples; and one of them^{396(c)} mentioned the sample to be unstable requiring investigations at 100 K. But in his publications P. C. Ray reported³⁹⁷ that the mercurous nitrite is sufficiently stable and can be crystallized out of its concentrated solution in hot water^{397(a)}, in which it suffers only *ca.* 20% decomposition (disproportionation)^{397(b)}. Obviously, the sample subjected to the X-ray study could not be identical to the one reported by P. C. Ray. The reported hydrolytic stability and stability to disproportionation suggest this to be a basic salt of mercury, and indeed a few such compositions³⁸⁹ agree with the analytical data on mercury and nitrogen reported by him. Being a grand-pupil of P. C. Ray I am no less respectful of him than any one else; but scientific assessment has to be free of any sentimental bias. P. C. Ray is great for several reasons³⁹⁸, we need not thrust greatness on him for the wrong reason. But some of the sub-normal valence state compounds of gold and platinum which P. C. Ray re-

ported, if structurally characterised by X-ray crystallography, are most likely found to be cluster compounds, similar to those of many of the presently known clusters of polyhedral structures³⁸⁹; and if that turns out to be true then that would establish P. C. Ray a pioneer in the field.

One of the favourite pupils of P. C. Ray, namely Priyadarajan Ray (P. Ray), carried out his masters mission much more successfully and is rightly acknowledged as the initiator of systematic research in modern inorganic chemistry in India. His research activities spanned a wide range, magnetochemistry, microanalytical chemistry, chemistry of complex compounds. Some of his significant contributions have been mentioned in some preceding sections.

In the words of P. C. Ray "Priyadarajan Ray is regarded as an acknowledged authority on complexes and valency and also on microchemistry and it is my practice to submit my own papers to his criticism and judgement before they are contributed to the chemical societies. My presidential addresses at the annual meetings of the Indian Chemical Society of 1926 and 1929 are based mainly upon his ideas and suggestions".

After his retirement from Calcutta University in the month of December 1952, P. Ray joined the newly established Inorganic Chemistry Department of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science (IACS) as Honorary Professor where he continued up to 1958. During this short period he succeeded in establishing this institute as an active centre of research in inorganic chemistry covering coordination chemistry and their important and useful analytical applications. In recognition of his contributions in microchemical and colorimetric methods of analysis he was elected (in 1951) one of the seven members of an International Commission of the International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry and was entrusted with the responsibility of preparing a comprehensive and critical report on colorimetric methods of analysis. He served this commission for 8 years and on being invited again to continue he declined suggesting that some young person be selected.

As evidence of recognition of his contributions to magnetochemistry the following opinion expressed (in 1950) by Prof. Wilhelm Klemm, Director, Anorganische

Chemisches Institut, University of Munster, Germany (then West Germany), who was an acknowledged authority on magnetochemistry, is worth noting :

"In giving an account of the modern developments (in magnetochemistry) in the field of Inorganic Chemistry I cannot conclude without referring to the contributions of the Indian workers in this field. Mention of names like Raman, Krishnan and P. Ray will be, in my opinion, suffice for the purpose".

Near the same location as that of the IACS, across the road, is Jadavpur University where A. K. Majumdar, a former associate of P. Ray, established a flourishing school of research in analytical chemistry since the 1940s. His contributions were mostly on new reagents for spectrophotometric estimations of various metal ions.

Apart from the research groups at Calcutta, several other centres of research activity in inorganic chemistry grew up in course of time, all over the country, and many of these made notable contributions and are keeping up the good tradition of research in various areas of modern inorganic chemistry. A full coverage of this would justify a separate article.

In a lecture on the "Status of Research in Inorganic Chemistry in India" delivered by the present author at the Indian Embassy in Tokyo (Japan) on April 12, 1980, on invitation of the Ashoka Forum of Japan, the following data on contributions from Indian institutions and univer-

Area	Annual publications (average for 1976-1978)
(A) Coordination Chemistry	
Preparations	25
Preparation and spectroscopic studies	1000
Detailed structural studies	250
Mechanisms of reactions	300
Theoretical studies	50
(B) Chemistry of f block elements :	
Lanthanids and Actinides	200
(C) Chemistry of s and p block elements	120
(D) Bioinorganic Chemistry	100
(E) Inorganic Analytical Chemistry (Mostly applications of complexes)	1680
(F) Miscellaneous	70

sities were presented, based on a report (1979) of the University Grants Commission (India) :

Of these total annual publications only *ca.* 8 per cent (overall average) were published in foreign journals. The data showed the then prevailing trend, but the overall position has not changed very much in the following decades.

Concluding remarks

Although the total number of annual publications by Indian chemists is fairly large, in terms of their citations in the *Annual Reports on the Progress of Chemistry* (ARPC, published by the Royal Society of Chemistry, RSC, UK) they are a very small fraction of the total number of citations that appear in that publication each year. Thus, in the ARPC, Sect. A (on Inorganic Chemistry) published in the year 2013, in which the developments during the year 2012 are highlighted, there are a total of a little over 3800 citations of which *ca.* 3 per cent are of Indian authors; three decades ago the corresponding figure was *ca.* 2 per cent. Some may argue that this is because majority of Indian chemists publish in Indian journals. This is not quite acceptable, as good quality publications (though very few in number) that were published in the low impact factor *Indian Journal of Chemistry* (published by the CSIR, New Delhi) and the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* (published by the said Society, Kolkata), and even the *Asian Journal of Chemistry*, during the last several decades had been cited in the ARPC of the RSC. The matter therefore needs serious introspection by all concerned.

It is indeed a pity that most of our promising research workers prefer to publish only in foreign journals, a trend particularly noticeable since the 1950s, which creams off much of the work of good quality. The standard of our national journals will never improve unless there is a change in this mindset. Good quality work of our chemists would not be less excellent if these are published in our national journals. Many of the distinguished chemists of India and other countries published most of their research work in their national journals of not very high impact factor. Thus, P. Ray published many of his well recognised work in the *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*; G. Schwarzenbach published most of his work in *Helv. Chim.*

Acta; J. Bjerrum, C. K. Jorgensen, C. J. Ballhausen similarly published mostly in *Acta Chem. Scand.*; but these are not less recognized by the scientific community.

References

- P. Ray, Chemistry in Ancient India, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1948, **25**, 327.
- D. Banerjea, "Progress of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India and its Impact on Medicine", Calcutta University, 2008.
- (a) B. N. Menshutkin, Historical Developments of the Concept of Chemical Elements, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1937, **14**, 59; (b) J. R. Partington, The Concepts of Substance and Chemical Element, *Chymia*, 1948, **1**, 109; (c) A. J. Ihde, "The Development of Modern Chemistry", Harper & Row, New York, 1964; Chap. 14 and 22 are specifically devoted to inorganic chemistry.
- R. N. Bhagvat, Knowledge of the Metals in Ancient India, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1933, **10**, 659.
- (i) H. M. Leicester, "Discovery of the Elements", 7th ed., *J. Chem. Educ.*, Easton, PA, USA, 1968.
- M. Camano *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2007, **99**, 0625021.
- T. Moeller, "The Chemistry of the Lanthanides", Pergamon Press, Elmsford, New York, 1975.
- K. R. Nash and G. R. Choppin (Eds.), "Separation of Elements", Plenum, New York, 1995. See also Ref. 9, Chap. 4.
- R. G. Bautista, in the "Handbook of the Physics and Chemistry of Rare Earths", (Eds.) A. Gschneidr (Jr.) and L. Eyring, North Holland, Amsterdam, Vol. 21, 1995.
- D. Banerjea, "Inorganic Chemistry: A Modern Treatise", Asian Books, New Delhi, 2012, Chap. 3.
- Y. T. Organessian *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2010, **104**, 142502.
- J. Khuyagbattar *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2014, **112**, 172501.
- (a) D. C. Hoffman, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 2009, **86**, 1122; (b) R. C. Barbes *et al.*, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2011, **83**, 1485; (c) M. Shadel, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2012, **100**, 579; (d) C. E. Dullmann, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2012, **100**, 67; (e) K. Morita *et al.*, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 2012, **81**, 103201; (f) K. Kramer, *Chem. World*, 2016, **13**(3), 10.
- (a) J. C. G. Bundi, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2006, **39**, 53; (b) M. Wood *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 500; (c) S. P. Faicke, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 524; (d) M. Bourill *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 557; (e) J. Y. Hycon *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **249**, 2287; (f) J. Gottfriedsen and F. T. Edelman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 2347.
- (a) F. T. Edelman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 2511; (b) S. A. Cotton, "Lanthanide and Actinide Chemistry", John Wiley, Chichester, 2006; (c) M. Ephritikhinn, *Dalton Trans.*, 2006, 12501; (d) I. Korobkov and S. Gambotta, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **54**, 321; (e) P. Carvan, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2006, **35**, 512; (f) F. T. Edelman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 343, 2515.
- (a) P. L. Arnold, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 9005; (b) A. S. P. Frey *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 6881; (c) S. M. Mansell *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 9036; (d) O. P. Lam *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 5965; (e) N. Tsoureas *et al.*, *Chem. Sci.*, 2014; DOI:10.1039/c4s01401d; (f) D. M. D'Allesandrea *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 6058; (g) See Ref. 150(b).
- (a) F. T. Edelman, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **256**, 1151, 2641; (b) F. T. Edelman *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2011, **255**, 1834.
- L. S. Natarajan, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **256**, 1583.
- J. V. Kratz *et al.*, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2011, **99**, 477.
- Y. Nagame and M. Hirata, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2011, **99**, 377.
- (a) S. Hofmann, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2011, **99**, 405; (b) Yu. Ts. Organessian, *Radiochim. Acta*, 2011, **99**, 429.
- (a) N. Jones, *Nature*, 2011, **472**, 22; (b) L. Sorace *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 3092.
- L. D. Carlos *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 536.
- B. Wang *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 3063.
- X. Wang *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 8127.
- J. Luzon and R. Sessoli, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 13556.
- R. Sessoli, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2012, **51**, 43.
- M. J. Manos and M. G. Kanatzidis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 16441.
- G. Tian *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 11579.
- S. A. Ansari *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 1751.
- J. A. Marinsky *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2781.
- W. Heitler and F. London, *Z. Phys.*, 1927, **44**, 455.
- J. C. Slater, *Phys. Rev.*, 1931, **37**, 481; 1931, **38**, 1109.
- L. Pauling (a) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 1367; (b) *Phys. Rev.*, 1932, **40**, 891; (c) "The Chemical Bond", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1967, Chap. 1-10.
- (a) R. G. Pearson, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1964, **23**, 1; (b) L. C. Allen, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1990, **23**, 175.
- F. Hund, *Z. Phys.*, 1928, **51**, 788, 793; *Z. Electrochem.*,

- 1928, **34**, 437.
36. R. S. Mulliken, *Chem. Rev.*, 1931, **9**, 347; *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1932, **4**, 1; *Science*, 1967, **157**, 13.
37. J. E. Lennard-Jones, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1929, **25**, 668.
38. (a) D. Banerjea, "Coordination Chemistry", 3rd. ed., Asian Books, New Delhi, 2009/2012, Chap. 2 and 4, and references cited therein; (b) For application of molecular orbital theory to complex compounds, see also H. B. Gray, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1964, **41**, 2.
39. N. V. Sidgwick and H. M. Powell, *Proc. Royal Soc.*, 1940, **A176**, 153.
40. (a) R. J. Gillespie and R. S. Nyholm, *Quart. Rev. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **11**, 339; (b) R. J. Gillespie, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5978; *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1963, **40**, 295; 1970, **47**, 18.
- 40(i). M. C. Durrant, *Chem. Sci.*, 2015; see *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(10), 29.
- 40(ii). G. Mana *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*, 2015, **44**, 031209; see *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(9), 23.
41. (a) H. Bethe, *Ann. Physik.*, 1929, [5]**3**, 133; (b) R. Schlapp and G. Penny, *Phys. Rev.*, 1932, **42**, 666; (c) J. H. Van Vleck, "Theory of Electric and Magnetic Susceptibilities", Oxford University Press, London, 1932; (d) R. Finkelstein and J. H. Van Vleck, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1940, **8**, 790; (e) F. A. Cotton, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1964, **41**, 466; (f) A. L. Companion and M. A. Komarynsky, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1964, **41**, 257; (g) For concepts and applications of the Ligand Field Theory to complex compounds, also see Ref. 38(a), Chap. 4.
42. (a) R. G. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3533; *Science*, 1966, **151**, 172; (b) R. G. Pearson, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1987, **64**, 561; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 734; *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **100**, 403; (c) R. G. Pearson, "Chemical Hardness", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 1997.
43. S. Yamada, and M. Tanaka, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 567.
44. R. G. Pearson, "Hard and Soft Acids and Bases", (Ed.) Dowden, Hutchinson and Ross, Stroudsville, PA (USA), 1973.
45. S. Ahrlad, J. Chatt and N. R. Davies, *Quart. Rev.*, 1958, **12**, 265.
46. (a) E. Grunwald and S. Winstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 846; (b) A. H. Fainberg and S. Winstein, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 2770; (c) see, P. R. Wells, *Chem. Rev.*, 1963, **63**, 171; (d) E. M. Kowoser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **80**, 3253; (e) K. Dimroth *et al.*, *Annalen.*, 1963, **661**, 1.
47. (a) V. Gutmann, "Coordination Chemistry in Non-aqueous Solution", Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1968; (b) V. Gutmann, "The Donor-Acceptor Approach in Molecular Interactions", Plenum, New York, 1978.
48. (a) V. Gutmann, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1976, **21**, 661; (b) V. Gutmann, *Chimia*, 1977, **31**, 1.
49. (a) R. S. Drago, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 1379; (b) R. S. Drago and B. B. Wayland, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 3571; (c) R. S. Drago *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 9.
50. D. Banerjea *et al.*, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1983, **13**, 63.
51. (a) C. G. Swain and C. B. Scott, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 141; (b) J. O. Edwards, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1540; 1956, **78**, 1819; (c) F. Basolo *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 241; (d) R. G. Pearson *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 319; (e) M. Cusumano *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1974, 489.
52. L. P. Hammett and A. J. Deyrup, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **54**, 2721.
- 52(i). (a) R. B. Woodward and R. Hoffmann, "The Conservation of Orbital Symmetry", Academic Press, New York, 1969; Verlag Chemie, GmbH, Weinheim, 1970; (b) R. Hoffmann and R. B. Woodward, *Science*, 1970, **167**, 825.
- 52(ii). (a) R. G. Pearson, *Theor. Chim. Acta*, 1970, **16**, 107; *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1971, **4**(4), 152; *Comp. & Maths. with Appls.*, 1986, **12B**, 236; (b) R. G. Pearson, "Symmetry Rules for Chemical Reactions", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1976; (c) R. G. Pearson, "Orbital Symmetry Rules and the Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", www.IUPAC.org/publications/pac/27/1/0145/pdf, 1971, pp. 145-166.
53. A. Stock, "Hydrides of Boron and Silicon", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, New York, 1933.
54. (a) R. E. Dickerson and W. N. Lipscomb, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1957, **27**, 212; (b) W. N. Lipscomb, in "Advances in Inorganic Chemistry and Radiochemistry", (Eds.) H. J. Emeleus and A. G. Sharpe, Academic Press, New York, 1959, Vol. 1, pp. 117-156; (c) W. N. Lipscomb, "Boron Hydrides", W. A. Benjamin, New York, 1963.
55. F. Jakle, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 1107.
56. F. Jakle, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 3985.
- 56(i). Z. Zhang *et al.*, *Chem. Sci.*, 2015; see *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(9), 27.
57. H. A. Hoppe *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2012, **51**, 6255.
58. E. Bernhardt *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 12085.
59. N. Bartlett, *Proc. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1962, 218.
60. (a) H. H. Hymann, (Ed.), "Noble Gas Compounds", The University of Chicago Press, Chicago, 1963; (b) J. H. Hollway, "Noble Gas Chemistry", Methuen,

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

- London, 1968.
61. (a) M. Tramsek *et al.*, *Solid State Science*, 2002, **4**, 9; *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 699; (b) M. Gerken *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 6069.
 62. (a) See Ref. 38(a), Chap. 2; (b) L. C. Wang *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 4392; (c) K. Seppelt, *Z. Anorg. Chem.*, 2003, **629**, 2427; (d) J. M. Thomas *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 1235; (e) S. A. Cooke and M. C. Gerry, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 17000.
 63. (a) G. Tavcar *et al.*, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 2004, **125**, 1579; *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 1452; (b) M. Tramsek *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, **43**, 699; (c) G. J. Schrobilgen *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 6069; (d) G. Tavcar and B. Zemva, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 1432; (e) G. K. Koyanagi and D. K. Bohme, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, 2010, **1**, 41.
 64. (a) S. Seidel and K. Seppelt, *Science*, 2000, **290**, 117; (b) T. Dews *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2002, **41**, 454.
 65. J. H. Lehmann *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **233-234**, 1.
 66. (a) A. Schlundt *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 4142; (b) J. M. Chambers *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 563.
 67. "Kirk-Othmer Encyclopedia of Chemical Technology", 3rd ed., Vol. 20, 1982, 4th ed., Vol. 5 and Vol. 6, 1993.
 68. (a) K. Abersfelder *et al.*, *Science*, 2009; *cf. Chem. World*, 2010, **7**(3), 33; (b) S. S. Sen *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2009, **48**, 8536; (c) S. Joseph, *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 2009, **48**, 8770.
 69. (a) E. G. Rochow, "Silicon", Chap. 15 in "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", (Eds.) J. C. Bailar (Jr.) *et al.*, Vol. 1, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1973; (b) E. G. Rochow, "Silicon and Silicones", Springer-Verlag, New Jersey, 1987.
 70. B. O'Regan and M. Gratzel, *Nature*, 1991, **353**, 737.
 71. M. Gratzel, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. C : Photochem. Rev.*, 2003, **4**(2), 145.
 72. H. Tributsch, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**(13-14), 1511.
 73. K. Hara and H. Arakawa, "Dye-Sensitised Solar Cells" in "Handbook of Photovoltaic Science and Engineering", Chap. 18, (Eds.) A. Luqui and S. Hegedus, John Wiley, New York, 2005.
 74. W. T. Haman *et al.*, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2008, **1**, 66.
 75. L. Moreira *et al.*, *Energy Environ. Sci.*, 2008, **1**, 605.
 76. M. Gratzel *et al.*, (a) *Inorg. Chem.*, 2005, **44**, 178; (b) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 6850; (c) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 4146; (d) *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **249**, 1460.
 77. M. Gratzel *et al.*, (a) *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **C111**(32), 11760; (b) *Nature Materials*, 2008, **7**(8), 626; (c) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 5930; (d) *ACS Nano*, 2009, **3**, 3103; (e) see Q. Yu *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2009, **C113**, 14559; (f) K. L. Wu *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 5124; (g) A. Raynal and E. Palomares, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, 4509.
 78. M. C. Scharber *et al.*, *Adv. Mater.*, 2006, **18**, 789.
 79. S. Gunnes *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **107**, 1324.
 80. Y. Y. Liang *et al.*, (a) *Nat. Photonics*, 2009, **3**, 649; (b) *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 56, 7792; (c) *Adv. Mater.*, 2010, **22**, E135.
 81. Y.-J. Cheng *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 5868.
 82. Y. Y. Liang and L. P. Yu, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, **43**, 1227.
 83. A. G. Tennyson *et al.*, *Macromolecules*, 2010, **43**, 6923.
 84. P. M. Beaujuge *et al.*, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2010, **43**, 1396.
 85. N. Allard *et al.*, *Macromolecules*, 2010, **43**, 2328.
 86. H. A. Saadeh *et al.*, *ACS Macro. Lett.*, 2012, **1**, 361.
 87. Y. Yang *et al.*, *Nature Photonics*, 2012, **6**, 180.
 88. A. C. Stuart *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **135**, 1806.
 89. M. L. Carriedo and M. L. Venezuela, *Macromolecules*, 2010, **43**, 226.
 90. J. C. Jang *et al.*, *J. Appl. Polymer Sci.*, 2007, **140**, 3120.
 91. A. Martin *et al.*, *Biomacromolecules*, 2010, **11**, 2268.
 92. (a) H. R. Alcock, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2010, **24**, 600; (b) M. Deng *et al.*, *Soft Matter*, 2010, **14**, 3119.
 93. F. Jakle *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 3985.
 94. (a) M. J. S. Dewar, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1951, **18**, C79; (b) J. Chatt and L. A. Duncanson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2939.
 95. (a) P. L. Pawson and T. J. Kealy, *Nature*, 1951, **168**, 1639; (b) S. A. Miller *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 632.
 96. J. S. Thayer, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1975 **13**, 1.
 97. P. Seiler and J. D. Dunitz, *Acta Cryst.*, 1979, **B35**, 1068.
 98. (a) E. O. Fischer and H. P. Fritz, *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1959, **1**, 56; (b) A. Streitwieser (Jr.) *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 7364; 1973, **95**, 8644; (c) J. C. Green, *Struct. Bonding*, 1981, **43**, 37.
 99. M. R. Taylor, *Compte. Rend. Chimie.*, 2006, **9**, 982.

100. R. H. Roesky *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2012, **31**, 7109.
101. J. Wessel *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1995, **34**, 2376.
102. See (a) Ref. 38(a), Chap. 5, and (b) Ref. 9, Chap. 20.
- 102(i). (a) R. N. Grimes, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 251; (b) W. Siebert, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1993, **35**, 187; (c) X. Wang *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **117**, 12227; (d) R. N. Grimes, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 1996, **10**, 209.
- 102(ii). E. Urnazius *et al.*, *Science*, 2002, **295**, 832.
- 102(iii). O. J. Scherer and T. Brack, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1987, **26**, 59.
- 102(iv). O. J. Scherer *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1986, **25**, 363.
103. J. W. Lauher and R. Hoffman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 1729.
104. E. O. Fischer and W. Hafner, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1955, **10b**, 665.
105. H. Zeiss *et al.*, "Benzenoid Metal Complexes", Ronald Press, New York, 1966.
106. E. L. Muetterties, *Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **82**, 499.
107. J. G. Brennan *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **111**, 2373; see also Ref. 98(b).
108. (a) H. H. Brintzinger *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 1997, **16**, 3413; (b) G. Fink *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**, 585; (c) W. Kaminsky and M. Arendt, *Adv. Polymer Sci.*, 1997, **127**, 143; (d) K. Ziegler *et al.*, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, **67**, 541; (e) G. Natta, *Atti. Accad. Naz. Lincei*, 1955, **14**, 61.
109. P. Molina *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 2005, 1159.
110. Y. Yu *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 2572.
111. J. W. Herndon, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **249**, 1889; 2009, **253**, 86, 103, 1517.
112. G. Wilkinson, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 1711.
113. L. Vaska and J. W. De Luzio, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 2784.
114. A. Bakac, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **250**, 2046.
115. Y. Le Mest and M. L'Her, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1995, 1441.
116. (a) M. Suzuki, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 609; (b) M. T. Kieber-Emmons *et al.*, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 618.
117. Several articles in a special issue of *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2007, **40**, 563, 573, 581, 593, 601.
118. (a) Ref. 9, pp. 1205 et seq; (b) F. Basolo, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1975, **8**, 384; (c) D. Banerjea and S. N. Poddar, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1951, **17**, 152.
119. J. P. Collman *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1974, **71**, 1325.
120. E. Tsuchida *et al.*, *Bioconjugate Chem.*, 2009, **20**, 1419.
121. (a) A. D. Allen and G. V. Senoff, *Chem. Commun.*, 1965, 621; (b) A. D. Allen *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 555.
122. J. Chatt *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, **78**, 589, and references cited therein.
123. (a) M. E. Vol'pin and V. B. Shur, *Doklady Acad. Nauk, SSSR*, 1964, **15**, 1102; (b) A. E. Shilov, in "Perspectives in Coordination Chemistry", (Eds.) A. F. Williams *et al.*, VCH, Weinheim, 1992, pp. 233-244.
124. E. E. Van Tamelen *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 7196.
125. H.-J. Himmel and M. Reiher, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **46**, 6264.
126. W. Kaim and B. Sarkar, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 9409.
127. (a) K. Arashiba *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.*, 2011, **3**, 120; (b) E. Kinoshita *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2012, **31**, 8437.
128. S. Hinrichsen *et al.*, *Annu. Rep. Prog. Chem., Sect. A*, 2012, **108**, 17.
129. (a) W. Massa *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1984, **23**, 149; (b) N. Wiberg and G. Ziegler, *Chem. Brit.*, 1978, **111**, 2123; (c) T. J. Meyer *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **124**, 4580; (d) W. J. Evas *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **125**, 10; (e) R. N. Butler *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2003, 1916; (f) K. O. Christe *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1999, **38**, 2004; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **123**, 6308; *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2003, **9**, 2840; (g) S. Fau *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2002, **106**, 4639.
130. P. C. Ford, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1981, **14**, 31.
131. (a) R. B. King *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 2985; (b) Y. Yoshida *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 3941; (c) P. C. Ford, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 4595; (d) C.-H. Cheng and R. Eisenber, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 5969; (e) R. M. Laine, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 6451, 6527.
132. (a) C. Kotal, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1983, **60**, 882; (b) B. O. Regan and M. Gratzel, *Nature*, 1991, **353**, 737; (c) T. Mallouk *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 926; (d) M. W. Kanan and D. G. Nocera, *Science*, 2008, **321**, 1072.
133. T. Komatsu *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 16297.
134. F. A. Armstrong *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 550.
135. (a) M. S. Dresselhaus and I. L. Thomas, *Nature*, 2001, **414**, 332; (b) L. Schlapbach and A. Züttel, *Nature*, 2001, **414**, 353.
136. T. K. Mandal and D. H. Gregory, *Annu. Rep. Prog.*

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

- Chem., Sect. A*, 2009, **105**, 2.
137. D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1117, and references cited therein.
138. C. Jin *et al.*, "Zeolites and Catalysis : Synthetic Reactions and Applications", John-Wiley, New York, 2010.
139. J. Shang *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 19246; see *Chem. World*, 2013, **10**(1), 34.
140. (a) Y. Hwang *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 4144; (b) F. Schroder *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 6119; (c) D. Farrussang *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 7502; (d) A. U. Czaja *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 1284; (e) L. J. Murray *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2009, **38**, 1294; (f) H. Kim *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 12200.
141. (a) J. Cezka (Ed.), "Metal-Organic Frameworks : Applications from Catalysis to Gas Storage", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2011; (b) J. C. Mendoz-Cortes *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2010, **A114**, 10824; 2011, **A115**, 1385; 2012, **A116**, 1621; (c) First report on hydrogen storage by an MOF : N. L. Rosi *et al.*, *Science*, 2003, **300**, 1127; (d) Zn-MOF selective and effective for scavenging CO₂ from gas mixtures : H. Kim *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 8401, 14168; (e) D. Britt *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, 2009; see *Chem. World*, 2010, **7**(1), 32; (f) Chiral MOF as heterogeneous catalyst for asymmetric synthesis, see J. S. Seo *et al.*, *Nature*, 2000, **404**, 982.
142. (a) J. L. C. Rowsell *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **126**, 5666; 2006, **128**, 726, 8136; (b) J. L. C. Rowsell and B. M. Yaghi, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 4670; (c) Y. Li *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2007, **C111**, 3405.
143. (a) R. Ramesh, *Nature*, 2009, **461**, 1218; (b) A. K. Cheetham *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 13625; (c) A. K. Cheetham *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, 2011, **108**, 6828; (d) A. K. Cheetham *et al.*, *Phys. Rev.*, 2012, **B86**, 214304; (e) G.-C. Xu *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 14948; (f) A. Stroppa *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 5847; (g) A. Stroppa *et al.*, *Adv. Mater.*, 2013, **25**, 2284; (h) A. Stroppa *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **135**, 18126.
144. (a) A. A. Talin *et al.*, *Science*, 2014, **343**, 66; (b) G. Frey and A. K. Cheetham, *Science*, 1999, **283**, 1125; (c) G. Frey *et al.*, *Science*, 2005, **309**, 2040; (d) A. K. Cheetham and C. N. R. Rao, *Science*, 2007, **318**, 58; (e) C. N. R. Rao, A. K. Cheetham and A. Thirumarugan, *J. Phys. Condens Matter*, 2008, **20**, 083202.
145. A. Ghosh *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 4265.
146. T. Dhanalakshmi *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 8317.
147. J. Rocha *et al.*, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 926.
148. (a) A. P. Cote *et al.*, *Science*, 2003, **310**, 1166; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 12914; (b) L. Pan *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2003, **42**, 542; (c) T. Uemura *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2006, **45**, 4122; 2007, **46**, 4987; (d) H. M. El Kaderi *et al.*, *Science*, 2007, **316**, 368; (e) S. S. Han *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **130**, 11580; (f) Y. Yan *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 1025.
149. (a) S. N. Riduan *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 3322; (b) R. Tanaka *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 14168; (c) U. J. Kilgore *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 487; (d) G. Albertin *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2006, **25**, 4235; (e) O. R. Allen *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2009, **28**, 2385; (f) T. Seki *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2009, 349.
150. (a) Pun So-Ngan *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2002, 575; (b) R. Angamathu *et al.*, *Science*, 2010, **327**, 313; (c) U. J. Vilgou *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 487; (d) J. M. Hooker *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 3482; (e) C. M. Moming *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 6643; (f) A. E. Ashley *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 9839.
- 150(i). J. Kothandaraman *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2016, **138**, 778.
151. O. T. Summerscales *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 9602.
152. T. Watanabe *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 3474.
153. R. A. Perutz *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 8189.
154. (a) H. W. Krato, R. E. Smalley, and two others, *Nature*, 1985, **318**, 162; (b) H. W. Krato, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1992, **31**, 111; (c) R. E. Smalley, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1992, **21**, 98; (d) E. C. Constable, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1994, **33**, 2369.
155. (a) H. W. Krato, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 1423; (b) W. Kratschmer *et al.*, *Nature*, 1990, **347**, 354; (c) M. A. Wilson *et al.*, *Nature*, 1992, **355**, 117; (d) P. R. Buek *et al.*, *Science*, 1992, **257**, 215; (e) T. K. Dalt *et al.*, *Science*, 1993, **259**, 1599; (f) R. Dagaqni, *Chem. & Eng. News*, August 1 (1994), pp. 4, 5.
156. (a) Ref. 9, Chap. 9, Sect. 9.5; (b) R. Taylor, *Compte. Rend. Chime.*, 2006, **9**, 982.
157. Y. Maeda *et al.*, *Nanoscale*, 2011, **3**, 2421.
158. A. M. Lopez *et al.*, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2011, **21**, 1305.
159. (a) J. S. Kolosanajaj *et al.*, "Bio-applications of Nanoparticles", Editon Edn., 2007, Vol. 620, pp. 168-180; (b) Y. Lin *et al.*, *Nanotechnology*, 2009, **20**, 10.
160. (a) R. Bakrey *et al.*, *Int. J. Nanomedicine*, 2007, **2**, 639; (b) R. Partha and J. L. Conyers, *Int. J.*

- Nanomedicine*, 2009, **4**, 261.
161. (a) P. Chaudhuri *et al.*, *ACS Nano*, 2009, **3**, 2505; (b) Y. Lin *et al.*, *Nanotechnology*, 2009, **20**, 10.
162. (a) B. Sitharaman and L. J. Wilson, *J. Biomed. Nanotechnology*, 2007, **3**, 342; (b) C. Y. Shu *et al.*, *Bioconjugate Chem.*, 2009, **20**, 1186.
163. (a) J. J. Yin *et al.*, *Mol. Pharma.*, 2008, **74**, 1132; (b) Y. Liu *et al.*, *Biomaterials*, 2009, **30**, 3934.
164. O. Stilova *et al.*, *Polymer*, 2007, **48**, 1835.
165. M. G. Alvarez *et al.*, *Int. J. Biochem. and Cell Biol.*, 2006, **38**, 2029.
166. I. M. Belousova *et al.*, *J. Optical Tech.*, 2009, **76**, 2243.
167. A. Kumar *et al.*, *Chemical & Biological Drug Design*, 2009, **73**, 553, 557.
168. O. A. Troshina *et al.*, *Org. Biomol. Chem.*, 2007, **5**, 2783.
169. A. B. Kornev *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 8298.
170. J. C. Jiang *et al.*, *J. Appl. Polymer Sci.*, 2006, **99**, 2874.
171. W. Q. Tian *et al.*, *J. Compt. Theor. Nanoscience*, 2009, **6**, 239.
172. E. M. Shpilevsky *et al.*, *Materialwiss. Werkstofftech.*, 2011, **42**, 59.
173. S. Florito, *Nanotechnology*, 2006, **6**, 591.
174. (a) B. I. Yakobson and R. E. Smalley, *Amer. Scientist*, 1997, **85**, 324; (b) A. N. Khlobystor, *ACS Nano*, 2011, **5**, 4306, and references cited therein.
175. J. M. Schnorr and T. M. Swager, *Chem. Mater.*, 2011, **23**, 646.
176. (a) S. Bag *et al.*, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 2011, **63**, 141; (b) S. Y. Madani *et al.*, *Int. J. Nanomed.*, 2011, **6**, 2963; (c) W. X. Zhang *et al.*, *Nanoscale Rev. Lett.*, 2011, **6**, 555; (d) S. K. Vashist *et al.*, *Carbon*, 2011, **49**, 4077.
177. (a) M. van der Zande *et al.*, *Tissue Eng. Part B : Rev.*, 2011, **17**, 57; (b) J. Kayal *et al.*, *Nanomed. : Nanotechnol. Biol. Med.*, 2011, **7**, 40; (c) L. A. Yan *et al.*, *Nanoscale*, 2011, **3**, 362.
178. O. Vittorio *et al.*, *Nanotechnology*, 2011, **22**, 095706.
179. Z. A. Liu *et al.*, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2011, **21**, 586.
180. B. Cola *et al.*, *Nat. Nanotechnol.*, 2015; see *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(11), 27.
181. K. S. Novoselov, A. K. Geim, and six others, *Science*, 2004, **306**, 666.
182. (a) W. Choi *et al.*, *Crit. Rev. Solid State Material Sci.*, 2010, **35**(1), 52; (b) J. H. Werner *et al.*, "Graphene : Fundamentals and Emergent Applications", Elsevier, New York, 2013.
183. See *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(7) 42.
- 183(i). (a) S. Hu *et al.*, *Nature*, 2014, **516**, 227; (b) M. Lozada-Hidalgo *et al.*, *Science*, 2015, **351**, 68.
184. K. Adamczyk *et al.*, *Science*, 2009, **326**, 1690.
185. H.-J. Zhai *et al.*, *Nat. Chem.*, 2014, **6**, 727; Photoelectron spectroscopic evidence for B₄₀ in the gaseous state has been furnished by L.-S. Wang, see *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(1), 25.
186. B. Z. Yakobson *et al.*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 2007, **98**, 166804.
187. (a) Y. Ma *et al.*, *Nanoscale*, 2014; see *Chem. World.*, 2014, **11**(8), 5; (b) J. Lu *et al.*, *Nanoscale*, 2014; see *Chem. World*, 2014, **11**(9), 30.
188. See *Chem. World*, 2015, **12**(1), 24, 25.
189. (a) M. Moscovitz (Ed.), "Metal Clusters", Wiley, New York, 1986; (b) D. M. P. Mingos and D. J. Wales, "Introduction to Cluster Chemistry", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ, 1990; (c) D. F. Shriver *et al.*, "The Chemistry of Metal Cluster Complexes", VCH, Weinheim, 1990; (d) P. Braunstein *et al.* (Eds), "Metal Cluster Chemistry", Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 1999.
190. P. Braunstein *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 911.
191. (a) J. Yu *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2008, **27**, 5800; (b) M. Carrasco *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 9754; (c) G. Gondzik *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 13599; (d) S. Schulz *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 7757.
192. (a) S. P. Green *et al.*, *Science*, 2007, **318**, 1754; (b) Y. Y. Liu *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 4210.
193. M. Weicko *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2007, 927.
194. M. P. Blake *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 15358.
195. A. F. Masters and J. T. Meyer, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **14**, 339.
196. (a) H. Schnockel *et al.*, *Nature*, 1997, **387**, 379; (b) X. Gong *et al.*, *Phys. Rev.*, 2000, **B62**, 15413; (c) A. Schnepf and H. Chnockel, *Angew. Chem.*, 2002, **114**, 3682.
197. (a) See, R. A. Kresinski, *Annu. Rep. Prog. Chem., Sect. A*, 2004, **100**, 66; (b) Ref. 191(c); (c) A Schnepf *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 7731; *Eur. Phys. J. D. : Atomic Mol. Opt. Phys.*, 2003, **24**, 3165; (d) A. Schnepf and H. Schnockel, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 711; (e) J. Frenzel *et al.*, *Phys. Rev.*, 2004, **B70**, 235404; (f) R. Koppe and H. Schnockel, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 2000, **626**, 1095.
198. (a) A. Gil *et al.*, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 8340; (b) M. Nyman and T. M. Alam, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 20131; (c) P. C. Burns *et al.*, *J. Am.*

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

- Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 1810; *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 2403, 7801; (d) P. Miro and C. Bo, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 3840.
199. A. Gil *et al.*, *Chem.-Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 8340.
200. R. Ababei *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 11295.
201. (a) G. Schmid *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1989, **28**, 778; (b) G. Schmid, *Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **92**, 1709, and references cited therein.
202. (a) Ref. 201(b); (b) G. Schmid, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 2321; *Mater. Chem. Phys.*, 1991, **29**, 133; (c) G. Schmid *et al.*, *Adv. Mater.*, 1990, **2**, 482; *J. Vac. Sci. Technol.*, 1991, **89**, 814.
203. P. D. Cluskey *et al.*, *Zeit. fur Physik. D. Atoms, Molecules and Clusters*, 26 (Supplement 1), SB-511 (1993), ISSN 0178-7683.
204. (a) B. T. Heaton *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 8106; (b) S. Martinengo *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1973, 651; *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1974, 299; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 7095; (c) S. R. Drake, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 455; (d) R. Y. Qi and J. D. Corbett, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1994, **33**, 5727.
205. D. J. Hinz and G. Meyer, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 125.
206. (a) A. Simon, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 159; (b) R. P. Ziebarth and J. Corbett, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1989, **22**, 256; (c) H. Mattausch *et al.*, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 1992, **616**, 157; (d) H. M. Arteld *et al.*, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 1992, **618**, 18.
207. (a) B. T. Heaton and T. Eguchi, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1999, 3523; (b) R. Bau *et al.*, *Science*, 1997, **275**, 1099.
208. (a) B. K. Teo *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 3494; (b) W.-G. Wang *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 1014.
209. (a) A. W. Castelman (Jr.) *et al.*, *Science*, 1992, **255**, 1411; (b) M. J. Bowers, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1994, **27**, 324.
210. (a) A. Smith and J. Sett, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1977, **2**(4), 229; (b) F. Hughes *et al.*, *Studies in Surface Science and Catalysis*, 1981, **7**(1), 418; (c) H. C. Clark and V. K. Jain, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1984, **55**, 151; (d) M. Ichikawa *et al.*, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1990, **62**(1), 15; (e) G. Swiss-Fink and G. Meister, *Adv. Organomet. Chem.*, 1993, **35**, 41; (f) L. H. Pignolet *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1998, **143**, 219; (g) R. D. Adams and F. A. Cotton (Eds.), "Catalysis by Di- and Polynuclear Metal Complexes", Wiley-VCH, New York, 1998; (h) D. Brann Stein and J. Rose, "Heterometallic Clusters for Heterogeneous Catalysis", Wiley-VCH, New York, 1998.
211. C. Femoni *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **350**, 1580.
212. G. Shon and U. Simon, *Colloid Polymer Sci.*, 1995, **273**, 101.
213. (a) Kouzlarich (Ed.), "Chemistry, Structure and Bonding in Zintl Phases and Ions", VCH, Weinheim, 1996; (b) S. C. Sevov and J. M. Goicoechea, *Organometallics*, 2008, **25**, 5678; (c) T. Fassler (Ed.), "Zintl Ions : Principles and Recent Developments", *Structure and Bonding*, Vol. 140, 2011; see also Vol. 139; (d) S. Scharfe *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 3630.
214. J. D. Corbett, *Chem. Rev.*, 1985, **85**, 383.
215. (a) S.-J. Kin *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, **46**, 3144; (b) W. Carillo-Cabrea *et al.*, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 2003, **629**, 601; (c) C. Kranenburg and A. Mewis, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 2003, **629**, 1023; (d) G. Frisch *et al.*, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 2003, **629**, 1661.
216. (a) S. Scharfe *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 3630; (b) T. F. Fassler and S. D. Hoffman, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 6400.
217. (a) J. D. Corbett, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 198; (b) R. E. Burns *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 3596; (c) A. Hershaft and J. D. Corbett, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, **2**, 878; (d) R. M. Friedma and J. D. Corbett, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1971, 421.
218. K. Wade, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1971, 792; *Chem. Brit.*, 1975, **11**, 177; *Adv. Inorg. Chem. Radiochem.*, 1976, **18**, 1.
219. (a) M. McPartlin and D. M. P. Mingos, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 1321; (b) M. McPartlin, *Polyhedron*, 1984, **3**, 1279; (c) D. M. P. Mingos, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1984, **17**(9), 311; (d) S. M. Owen, *Polyhedron*, 1988, **7**, 253.
220. (a) F. A. Cotton *et al.*, "Multiple Bond between Metal Atoms", 3rd, ed., Springer, Berlin, 2005; (b) F. A. Cotton, in "Perspectives in Coordination Chemistry", (Eds.) F. A. Williams *et al.*, VCH, Weinheim, 1992, pp. 321-332; (c) M. H. Chisholm, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1986, **25**, 21; (d) F. A. Cotton, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1983, **60**, 713; (e) W. C. Trogler, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1980, **57**, 424.
221. (a) S. Ritter, *Chem. & Eng. News*, September 26, 2005, Vol. 83, No. 39; (b) P. P. Power *et al.*, *Science*, 2005, **310**, 844; (c) Y.-C. Tsai *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **131**, 12534; (d) L. C. Wu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 2011, **A115**, 12602; (e) T.-C. Tsai *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 7250, 9933; (f) R. Kempe *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **47**, 7246; (g) P. P. Power *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, **46**, 11277; (h) K. H. Theopold *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 14162.
222. B. Oelkers *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2012, **18**, 13566.

- 222(i).(a) J.-M. Lehn, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1990, **29**, 1304; (b) F. Vogtle, "Supramolecular Chemistry", Wiley, Chichester, 1991; (c) J. S. Linbrey, *New J. Chem.*, 1991, **15**, 153; (d) C. M. Whitesides, *Science*, 1991, **254**, 1312; (e) G. R. Desiraju, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1994, **106**(3), 593; (f) J.-M. Lehn, "Supramolecular Chemistry Concepts and Perspectives", VCH, New York, 1995; (g) D. Philip and J. F. Stoddart, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1996, **35**, 1154; (h) S. R. Batten and R. Robson, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1998, **37**, 1460.
- 222(ii).(a) D. S. Amabilino *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 3905; (b) D. N. Reinhoudt *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1998, **4**, 1349; (c) J. de Mendoza, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1998, **4**, 1373; (d) J. P. Sauvage *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1996, 1915, 2005; 1997, 35; (e) J. P. Sauvage *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **118**, 9110; (f) J. P. Sauvage *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1996, **35**, 1119; (g) P. J. Lusby, *Annu. Rep. Prog. Chem., Sect. A*, 2008, **104**, 297; 2009, **105**, 323; 2010, **106**, 319; 2011, **107**, 297; 2012, **108**, 292; 2013, **109**, 254.
223. (a) C. N. R. Rao (Ed.), "Chemistry of High Temperature Superconductors", World Scientific, Singapore, 1991; (b) T. A. Vanderah (Ed.) "Chemistry of High Temperature Superconductors", Noyes, 1991; (c) J. I. S. Irvine, "Superconducting Materials", in "Insight into Speciality Inorganic Chemicals", (Ed.) D. Thompson, RSC, Cambridge (UK); J. K. Burdett, Structure, Compositions and Properties of High Temperature Cuprate Superconductors, in "Perspectives in Coordination Chemistry", (Ed.) A. F. Williams *et al.*, VCH, Weinheim, 1992, p. 293; (d) Several articles in *Chem. Brit.*, 1994, **30**, 722-748; (e) J. M. Williams *et al.*, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1988, **21**, 1; (f) A. W. Sleight, *Science*, 1988, **242**, 1519; (g) C. N. R. Rao *et al.*, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1989, **22**, 106; (h) C. N. R. Rao, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1989, **40**, 291.
224. (a) R. J. Cava, *Science*, 1990, **247**, 656; (b) G. F. Holland and A. M. Stacy, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1988, **21**, 8; (c) P. Halder *et al.*, *Science*, 1988, **241**, 1198; (d) L. C. Porter *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 1645; (e) E. M. Engler *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 2848; (f) M. F. Garbauskas *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 871.
225. (a) J. G. Bednorz and K. A. Muller, *Z. Phys.*, 1986 **B64**, 189; *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1988, **60**, 585 (Nobel Lecture); (b) M. K. Wu, C. W. Chu and others, *Phys. Rev. Lett.*, 1987, **58**, 908.
226. (a) J. Chatt and J. R. Dillworth, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1974, 508; (b) J. Chatt, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1977, **49**, 815; (c) J. Chatt *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 1; (d) T. J. Greenough *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 1036; (e) K. K. Pandey, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **40**, 2145; (f) K. K. Pandey *et al.*, *Polyhedron*, 1995, **13-14**, 1987.
227. (a) C. V. Broadhurst, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1801; (b) K. J. Klabunde *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **88**, 391; (c) H. Werner, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1990, **25**, 1077; (d) D. F. R. Gilson *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 322; 1994, **33**, 804.
228. J. Chatt *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 343.
229. G. J. Kubas *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 451.
230. L. M. Venanzi *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1974, **13**, 133; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **67**, 65.
231. (a) P. Ray and R. M. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 118; (b) P. Ray, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1930, **79**, 94; see P. Ray, *J. and Proc. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1951, **23**, 49.
232. (a) J. Xavier and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 432, 589, 633, 725; (b) P. Ray and J. Xavier, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 535.
233. P. Ray, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, **63**, 313.
234. (a) A. K. De, N. N. Ghosh and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 493; (b) D. Banerjee, N. N. Ghosh and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **29**, 157.
235. (a) D. Sen, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969 2900; (b) L. Coghi *et al.*, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1978, **3**, 69.
236. (a) D. Sen, *Sci. & Cult.*, 1961, **27**, 501; (b) S. P. Ghosh *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **38**, 179; *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 573; (c) D. Banerjee and P. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 373; (d) D. Banerjee and S. Sengupta, *Z. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*, 1973, **397**, 215; (e) D. Sen and C. Saha, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 1976, 776.
237. S. R. Cooper *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1992, 894.
238. M. M. Ray and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, **35**, 601.
239. P. Ray and K. Chakravarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 47.
240. (a) D. Sen, N. N. Ghosh and P. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **27**, 619; (b) R. N. Banerjee and D. Banerjee, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, **17A**, 246.
241. N. R. Kunchur, *Nature*, 1968, **217**, 539.
242. See D. M. P. Mingos, in "Modern Coordination Chemistry: The Legacy of Joseph Chatt", (Eds.) G. J. Leigh and N. Winterton, RSC, Cambridge, 2012, p. 69.
243. R. S. Nyholm *et al.*, *Nature*, 1964, **201**, 1322.
- 243(i).(a) R. S. Nyholm and D. V. Ramana Rao, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 130; (b) H. L. Nigam, R. S.

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

- Nyholm and D. V. Ramana Rao, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1397; (c) H. L. Nigam, R. S. Nyholm and M. H. B. Stiddard, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1893.
244. W. Levason and G. Reid, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 2565.
245. P. Ray and N. K. Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **20**, 81.
246. J. C. Bailar (Jr.), *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **42**, 201.
247. C. S. Springer (Jr.) and R. E. Sievers, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1967, **6**, 852.
248. D. Banerjea and J. C. Bailar (Jr.), *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 331; see also D. Banerjea, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1988, **13**, 160.
249. J. C. Bailar (Jr.) *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1980, **42**, 201.
250. A. Y. Girgis and R. C. Fay, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 7051.
251. A. Rodger and B. F. G. Johnso, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 3062.
252. (a) R. C. Mehrotra *et al.*, "Metal beta-Diketonates and Related Derivatives", Academic Press, London, 1978; (b) V. K. Jain, R. Bohra and R. C. Mehrotra, *Syn. React. Inorg. Met. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **9**, 491; *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1980, **184**, 57; *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **44**, L265; (c) D. A. Thornton, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **104**, 173.
253. R. F. Sievers *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1993, **128**, 285.
254. A. Salzer *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **34**, 6231, and references cited therein.
255. L. L. Borer and E. Sinn, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 2514.
256. (a) H. Chisholm, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1995, 79; (b) A. Herrmann *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1995, **34**, 2187; (c) W. G. Van der Sluys and A. P. Sattelberger, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 1027; (d) K. G. Caulton and L. G. Hubert, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 969; (e) R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 1996, 1.
257. D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra and D. P. Gaur, "Metal Alkoxides", Academic Press, London, 1978.
258. (a) D. M. Roundhill, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **43**, 533; (b) A. Ikeda and S. Shinkai, *Chem. Rev.*, 1997, **97**, 1713.
259. L. Echegoyen *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **116**, 3580.
260. G. Cafeo *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 1207.
261. J. M. Lehn, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 49; *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 871.
262. C. H. Park and H. E. Simmons, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 2431.
263. E. Garf and J. M. Lehn, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 6403.
264. J. M. Lehn, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1976, **4**, 49; *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1979, **62**, 2763; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 89.
265. P. A. Tasker *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 1999, 2077; *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton.*, 2000, 3773; Proc. 35 Int. Conf. Coord. Chem., Heidelberg, 2002, pp. 154, 852; see also, P. D. Bur and P. A. Gale, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 486.
266. H. Zhao and F. P. Gabbai, *Nat. Chem.*, 2010, **2**, 984.
267. D. L. Kepert, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **23**, 1.
268. R. Eisenberg and J. A. Ibers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 3776; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 411.
269. M. Bennett *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 7504.
270. C. J. Pedersen, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 1021.
271. J. M. Lehn, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1988, **27**, 89.
272. A. M. Sargeson *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 3181; 1982, **104**, 6015; 1983, **105**, 4652, 5503; 1984, **106**, 8282; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, **22**, 2010, 3554; 1985, **24**, 2325; 1986, **25**, 865; *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1992, **45**, 1081; *Chem. Eur. J.*, 1997, **3**(8), 1283.
273. J. L. Dye *et al.*, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, **32**, 327; *Scientific American*, 1987, **257**(3), 66; *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 3781; 1986, **108**, 3534; 1987, **109**, 5561; 1991, **113**, 1605.
274. (a) J. L. Dye, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1977, **54**, 323; *Science*, 2003, **301**, 607; (b) J. L. Dye *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **108**, 3534; 1993, **115**, 9542; *Acta Cryst., Sect. C : Cryst. Struct. Commun.*, 1988, **C44**, 1374.
275. J. Luo *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 9508.
276. X. L. Zhang *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 2325.
277. P. Kaur *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 8767.
278. C. A. Kraus, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **29**, 1557.
279. E. J. Hart and J. W. Boag, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 4090.
280. E. J. Hart, *Science*, 1964, **146**, 19.
281. J. H. Blaxendale, *Radiation Res. Suppl.*, 1964, **4**, 139.
282. E. J. Hart *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 1524; 1966, **70**, 150.
283. M. Anbar and E. J. Hart, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 973.
284. L. M. Dorfman and M. S. Matgheson, *Prog. React.*

- Kinetics*, 1965, **3**, 239.
285. "Solvated Electron", in *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, Vol. 50, ACS, Washington, D.C., 1965.
286. G. D. Venerable, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 1999.
287. M. Kulkarni *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 6185.
288. F. Vogtel and E. Weber, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1974, **13**, 814.
289. B. F. Abrahams *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2007, **46**, 8640; *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2008, **48**, 3129.
290. H. A. Goodwin, in "Chelating Agents and Metal Chelates", (Eds.) F. P. Dwyer and D. P. Mellor, Academic Press, New York, 1964, p. 143.
291. S. Kido *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 953.
292. F. P. Dwyer and F. Lions, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2917; 1950, **72**, 1545.
293. G. Schwarzenbach *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 331; 1949, **32**, 839; 1950, **33**, 974; 1953, **36**, 581.
294. J. Rebecck (Jr.) *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 5192.
295. See, Ref. 38(a), Chap. 3.
296. (a) H. B. Kagan, in "Comprehensive Organometallic Chemistry", (Eds.) G. Wilkinson *et al.*, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1982, Vol. 8, pp. 463-498; (b) B. Bosnich and M. D. Fryzuk, *Top. Stereochem.*, 1982, **12**, 119; (c) H. Brunner, *Top. Stereochem.*, 1988, **18**, 129; (d) J. W. Scott, *Top. Stereochem.*, 1989, **19**, 209; (e) E. N. Jacobson *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 6703; (f) R. Noyori and H. Takaya, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1990, **23**, 345.
297. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.
298. "Stability Constants of Metal Ion Complexes", Spl. Publ., No. 17 (1964), No. 25 (1971), (Eds.) L. G. Sillen and A. E. Martell, The Chemical Society, London.
299. "Critical Stability Constants", Vols. 1-4 (1974-1977), Vol. 5 (1982), Vol. 6 (1989), Plenum Press, New York.
300. See Ref. 38(a), Chap. 3.
301. (a) H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, *Nature*, 1948, **162**, 746; (b) M. Calvin and N. C. Melchior, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270; (c) H. Sigel and D. B. McCormick, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1970, **3**, 201.
302. (a) G. Schwarzenbach, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1952, **35**, 2344; (b) D. Munro, *Chem. Ber.*, 1977, **110**, 100; (c) R. T. Myers, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 952; (d) R. D. Hancock and A. E. Martell, *Comment. Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **6**, 237; (e) A. E. Martell, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **133**, 39.
303. (a) F. P. Hinz and D. W. Margerum, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **96**, 4993; *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 2841; (b) G. F. Smith and D. W. Margerum, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1975, 807.
304. See, Ref. 38(a), Chap. 8.
305. H. Sigel (Ed.), "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", Vols. 1-44, (1974-2006), Marcel Dekker, New York.
306. See, Ref. 38(a), Chap. 7; see also Ref. 9, different Chapters on metallic elements.
307. A. Aitio *et al.*, "Trace Elements in Health and Disease", RSC, Cambridge, UK, 1991.
308. C. Andrecini *et al.*, *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **13**, 1205.
309. (a) D. C. Rees *et al.*, *Adv. Inorg. Chem.*, 1993, **40**, 89; (b) see, J. B. Howard and D. C. Rees, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 2965.
310. D. R. Adams *et al.*, Nitric Oxide : Physiological Role, Biosyntheses and Medical Uses, in "Progress in the Chemistry of Organic Natural Products", (Eds.) W. Herz *et al.*, Springer, New York, 1992, No. 76.
311. B. Kurzak *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1992, **114**, 169.
312. (a) A. M. Wright *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 14336; (b) B. Mondal *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 1251.
313. B. Rosenberg *et al.*, *Nature*, 1969, **222**, 385.
314. (a) E. R. Jamieson and S. J. Lippard, *Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **99**, 2467; (b) Z. J. Guo and P. J. Sadler, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1999, **38**, 1513.
315. B. W. Harper *et al.*, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2010, **16**, 7064.
316. L. Dvornak *et al.*, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, 3441.
317. H. E. Abdou *et al.*, *Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **253**, 1661.
318. K. M. Hindi *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **109**, 3859.
319. A. Levina *et al.*, *Metalomics*, 2009, **1**, 458.
320. S. Murie *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 11344.
321. A. Kaskatan-Ebioglu *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **251**, 884.
322. S. Ray *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **129**, 15042.
323. P. J. Barnard and S. J. Berners-Price, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **251**, 1889.
324. P. K. Jain *et al.*, *Nano Today*, 2007, **2**, 18.
325. I. Ozdemir *et al.*, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2010, **363**, 3803; *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2010, **24**, 758.
326. S. J. Tan *et al.*, *Future Med. Chem.*, 2010, **2**, 1591.
327. A. Casini *et al.*, Organometallic Antitumour Agents with Alternative Modes of Action, in "Topics in Organometallic Chemistry", Vol. 32, Springer, 2010.
328. S. Nobili *et al.*, *Med. Res. Rev.*, 2010, **30**, 550.
329. I. Otto *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **54**, 763.

Banerjea : Origin and progress in Inorganic Chemistry

330. C. P. Bagowski *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 10799.
331. G. Khan and S. Merajver, *Expert. Opin. Investig. Drugs*, 2009, **18**, 541.
332. G. Pelasi *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **53**, 8765.
333. (a) A. A. Neju *et al.*, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2009, **362**, 3993; (b) J. Nilson *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 7902.
334. M. R. Maurya, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 1260.
335. A. Maniatakoid *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2009, **103**, 859.
336. A. Kumar *et al.*, *ACS Chem. Neuroscience*, 2010, **1**, 691.
337. (a) C.-M. Che and R. W.-Y. Sun, *Chem. Commun.*, 2011, **47**, 9554; (b) S. J. Berners-Price and A. F. Filipovaka, *Metallomics*, 2011, **3**, 863; (c) "Gold-based Therapeutic Agents : A New Perspective", (Ed.) S. J. Berner-Price, Wiley, New York, 2011.
338. J. Reedjik *et al.*, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2011, **366**, 81.
339. J. Coetzee *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 1471.
340. S. Wang *et al.*, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 1914.
341. L. Cattaruzza *et al.*, *Int. J. Cancer*, 2011, **128**, 206.
342. B. D. Glisie *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 6887.
343. W. J. Youngs *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 327.
344. (a) M. Pellei *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 9873; (b) W. Liu *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **55**, 3713; (c) H. Sivaram *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2012, **31**, 5875; (d) D. C. F. Monteiro *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 3720; (e) E. Eloy *et al.*, *Chem. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **7**, 805; (f) F. Hackenberg *et al.*, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2012, **717**, 123.
345. (a) E. Schuh *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **55**, 5518; (b) B. D. Wright *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 6500; (c) A. Tabacaru *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 9775; (d) M. McCann *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 6516; (e) F. R. G. Bergamini *et al.*, *RSC Adv.*, 2012, **2**, 10372; see *Annu. Rep. Prog. Chem.*, 2013, **A109**, 193.
346. (a) J. Z. Lu *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2012, **112**, 39; (b) H. El.Moll *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **59**, 7921.
347. *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **256** (19-20), 2127-2396.
348. G. J. Brewer, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2012, **393**, 135.
349. *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**(21), 6321-6580.
350. K. Sahin *et al.*, *Biol. Trace. Elem. Res.*, 2012, **150**, 291.
351. L. E. Evers *et al.*, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 269.
352. Z. Li *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2011, **40**, 2062.
353. J. Esteltan *et al.*, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 4934.
354. (a) B. N. Ahamed *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2010, **49**, 4447; (b) C. S. Lim *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2010, **46**, 2388.
355. H. Zheng *et al.*, *Chem. Commun.*, 2012, **48**, 2243.
356. P. Molina *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton*, 2005, 1159.
357. (a) A. Werner, *Ann.*, 1912, **386**, 1; (b) A. Werner, *Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 1228, 3061.
358. F. A. Long, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 570; 1941, **63**, 1353.
359. R. Charonnat, *Ann. Chim.*, 1931, **16**, 202.
360. C. H. Johnson and A. Mead, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, **31**, 1621.
361. (a) A. B. Lamb and J. W. Marden, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **33**, 1873; (b) A. B. Lamb and I. F. Fairhall, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 378; (c) A. B. Lamb, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 699.
362. (a) F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions : A Study of Metal Complexes in Solution", Wiley, New York, 1958; 2nd ed., 1967; (b) C. H. Langford and H. B. Gray, "Ligand Substitution Processes", Benjamin, New York, 1965; (c) M. L. Tobe (Ed.), M. T. P. Int. Rev. Sci., Inorganic Chemistry, Series 1, Vol. 9, "Reaction Mechanisms in Inorganic Chemistry", Butterworths, London, 1972, Series 2, 1973; (d) R. G. Wilkins, "The Study of Kinetics and Mechanisms of Reactions of Transition Metal Complexes", Allyn and Bacon, Boston, 1974; 2nd ed., VCH, Weinheim, 1991.
363. (a) F. Basolo, *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, 1967, **62**, 402; (b) R. D. Archer, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 243; (c) C. H. Langford, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1969, **46**, 557; (d) D. Banerjea, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 97; (e) D. Banerjea, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1987, **26A**, 543.
364. (a) D. Banerjea, *Proc. Indian Nat. Sci. Acad., Sect. A*, 1996, **62**, 77; (b) D. Banerjea, *J. Asiatic Soc.*, 2001, **43**(1), 1; (c) D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 459; (d) M. Bassetti, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, 4473.
365. (a) B. Sickluka, *Prog. React. Kinet.*, 1998, **24**, 165; (b) R. Van Eldik, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **182**, 373; (c) P. Banerjee, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1999, **192**, 19.
366. D. Banerjea and K. K. Tripathi, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1958, **7**, 78.
367. D. Banerjea, F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **79**, 4055.
368. F. Jalilehvand and L. J. Laffin, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2008, **47**, 3248.
369. D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2015, **92**, 1319.
370. M. Basak and D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2015, **92**, 1617.
371. (a) M. Eigen, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 115; *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 1963, **6**, 97; (b) M. Eigen and K. Tamm, *Ber. Bunsenges. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**,

- 107; (c) M. Eigen and R. G. Wilkins, *Adv. Chem. Ser.*, No. 49, ACS, Washington, D.C., 1965
372. (a) H. Taube *et al.*, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4118; (b) H. Taube and H. Meyers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **76**, 2103; (c) H. Taube and E. S. Gould, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1969, **2**, 321.
373. R. A. Marcus, *Annu. Rev. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **15**, 155.
374. (a) V. Balzani and V. Carasiti, "Photochemistry of Coordination Compounds", Academic Press, New York, 1970; (b) R. B. Bucat and D. W. Watts, *Inorganic Photochemistry*, in "Inorganic Chemistry Series One", M. T. P. International Review of Science, Vol. 9, (Ed.) M. L. Tobe, Butterworths, London, 1972, Chap. 5; (c) A. W. Adamson and P. D. Fleischauer, "Concepts of Inorganic Photochemistry", Wiley, New York, 1975.
375. (a) Z. Cui and R. A. Henderson, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2006, **31**, 530; (b) A. D. Allian *et al.*, *Organometallics*, 2006, **25**, 2182.
376. S. Anbu *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 12970.
377. R. Banerjee *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2009, 5469.
378. K. Mandal and R. Banerjee, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 2714.
379. R. van Eldik *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 1695.
380. D. Olmstead *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 1375.
381. A. Gunay and K. H. Theopold, *Chem. Rev.*, 2010, **110**, 1030.
382. J. Seo and E. Kin, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 7951.
383. M. Chakraborty *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2011, **115**, 4882.
384. (a) S. J. Smith *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2012, **51**, 2065; (b) J. Kalmar *et al.*, *Dalton Trans.*, 2012, **41**, 11875.
385. B. F. E. Curchod and F. P. Rotzinger, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **50**, 8728.
386. J. T. O'Brien and E. R. Williams, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2011, **115**, 14612.
387. D. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 1011.
388. D. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 269.
389. D. Banerjee, *Eur. Chem. Bull.*, 2014, **3(2)**, 146.
390. P. C. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, **1**, 63.
391. (a) P. C. Ray and K. C. Bose Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 178; (b) P. C. Ray *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **3**, 358; (c) P. C. Ray *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **5**, 139; (d) P. C. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 89; (e) P. C. Ray *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 251; 1933, **10**, 275.
392. P. C. Ray, *J. Asiatic Soc. Bengal*, 1896, **65**, 1.
393. R. A. Potts and A. L. Allred, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1066.
394. D. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 1018.
395. R. D. Hancock *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2009, **48**, 11724.
396. (a) R. B. English *et al.*, *Acta Cryst. (C)*, 1985, **41**, 997; (b) S. Ohba *et al.*, *Acta Cryst. (C)*, 1986, **42**, 1; (c) A. Chakravorty *et al.*, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2011, **50A**, 137.
397. (a) P. C. Ray, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1897, **71**, 337; (b) P. C. Ray, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1905, **87**, 171.
398. D. Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **88**, 1065.